

D7.3 Final Impact Assessment Report

Project ref. no.	H2020-MG-2018-SingleStage-INEA N° 824326
Project title	Revealing fair and actionable knowledge from data to support women's inclusion in transport systems.
Project duration	1 st November 2018 – 31 st January 2022 (39 months)
Website	www.diamond-project.eu
Related WP/Task	WP7 / T7.1 and T7.2
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document due date	30/10/2021 (M36)
Actual delivery date	26/11/2021 (M37)
Deliverable leader	ENU
Document status	Submitted

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 824326

Revision History

Version	Date	Author	Contribution
0.1	01/04/2021	Ababio-Donkor, Augustus (ENU)	Document Structure circulated to partners
0.2	05/08/2021	Ababio-Donkor, Augustus (ENU) Wafaa Saleh (ENU)	
0.3		Milenkovic, Milos (FTTE)	Productive Equity Analysis
0.4	21/09/2021	Filomena Mauriello (RINA)	Replicability of Results to Other Transport Context
0.5		Sara Poveda-Reyes (AITEC) Ashwani Kumar Malviya (AITEC) Elena García-Jiménez (AITEC) Francisco E. Santarremigia (AITEC)	Sensitivity and sustainability analysis (gender, over time, over space), and calculation of efficiency
0.6	15/10/2021	Ababio-Donkor, Augustus (ENU) Wafaa Saleh (ENU)	First draft version of document
0.7	18/10/2021	Ababio-Donkor, Augustus (ENU) Wafaa Saleh (ENU) Milos Milenkovic (FTTE)	Draft version circulated for internal review by partners
0.8	19/10/2021	Elena García-Jiménez (AITEC) Sara Poveda-Reyes (AITEC) Francisco E. Santarremigia (AITEC)	Revision
0.9	29/10/2021	Manuela Di Marino (RINA)	Legislation and Standards' opportunities
1.0	09/11/2021	Ababio-Donkor, Augustus (ENU) Wafaa Saleh (ENU) Milos Milenkovic (FTTE)	Second draft version of document
1.1	11/11/2021	Miguel Hervás Peralta (AITEC) Gemma D. Molero Prieto (AITEC) Francisco E. Santarremigia (AITEC)	Revision
1.2	23/11/2021	Ababio-Donkor, Augustus (ENU) Wafaa Saleh (ENU)	Final Version of Document
1.3	26/11/2021	Patricia Castillo (EUT)	Final preparation for submission.

Executive Summary

This document is deliverable, D7.3 “Final impact assessment report”. Deliverable 7.3 defines the framework and methodology for assessing the impact of the DIAMOND project and the extent to which the objective(s) are achieved. This specific objective is directly linked to the main issues identified in each of the use-cases (“Deliverable D2.2 Methodology and Conceptual framework”):

- ◆ Use Case I - Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways)
- ◆ Use Case II: Autonomous vehicles
- ◆ Use Case III: Bike Sharing services
- ◆ Use Case IV: Employment of Women in Rail Industry and Freight/CSR Protocols

The proposed framework for the impact assessment is in two folds;

- ◆ Productive Equity Assessment and
- ◆ Sensitivity Analysis.

The Productive Equity Assessment identifies, measures, and assesses the Equity, Effectiveness and Efficiency (the 3Es) Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for each Use Case.

Two types of sensitivity analysis are conducted:

- ◆ Sensitivity analysis over time and
- ◆ Sensitivity analysis over space.

The Sensitivity Analysis assesses the robustness of results (Top10 FCs) and fairness measures over time and over space. The outputs from the sensitivity analysis have been used to build the impact reports in this deliverable (D7.3).

Summary Findings:

The Fairness characteristics (as identified in WP3 and WP4) are the core of the DIAMOND analysis, and this impact assessment report. Generally, the key findings relate to the Aim of DIAMOND and closely follow the Fairness Characteristics (FCs). The results across the multiple research methods and the intersectional analysis suggest the following conclusions:

Use Case I: Public transport

In assessing the impact of the FCs on equity with respect to public transport (UC I), the results suggest that women particularly have accessibility challenges, which should be understood in the context of special needs relating to the family and caring responsibilities that women negotiate with in their daily routines. Specific attention should focus on level of services (accessibility and availability), safety and security, and information provision. The key FCs with the potential to deliver equity for women as users of public transport services relates to accessibility of the stations (such as ramps, escalators and lifts for persons with disabilities) which corresponds to “FC I14: Adapt the station access with ramps, escalators and lifts for users with special needs.”, “FC I12: Coordinated timetables between the different transport modes in the stations.” and “FC I11: Availability of information that indicate and allows access to key destination. The results show that 43% of FCs remained in the top 10 FCs from the analysis of Vertex I of the Inclusion Diamond (Public transport Today) and 67% for Vertex 3 (Public transport tomorrow, under the futuristic scenario of Hyperloop). The results indicate

20-80% of the top 10 FCs changed in the hierarchized list in both vertexes, therefore the Top 10 FCs of UC I are sustainable in the mid-term.

40% of Top 10 FCs for POLISH and SPANISH women are different in the UC I, perhaps due to the significant difference between the POLISH and the SPANISH railways infrastructures, as has been shown after the ANOVA analysis. The results can be easily used in fields like aviation, logistic or maritime transport.

Use Case II: *Autonomous Vehicles*

In assessing the impact of the FCs on equity in relation to Autonomous Vehicles (UC II), the results suggest that women are particularly concerned about safety and security and the performance of simultaneous tasks whilst travelling. In relation to women's use of autonomous vehicles, the most important fairness measures include education about sportive driving mode "FC637: Education about sportive driving mode when it is activated: Benefits and disadvantages", "FC6327: Automated system for speed controlling" and "FC219: Dissemination and promotional campaigns about safety mechanisms in the case of bad weather." have a higher equity score.

The results also show that 70% of FCs remained the in the top 10 FCs of Vertex 2 of the Inclusion Diamond (autonomous driving under Level 4+) and 78% for Vertex 4 (autonomous driving over Level 4+). The results indicate that less than 20% of the top 10 FCs changed from the analysis in both vertexes. Therefore, the Top 10 FCs of UC II are sustainable in the mid-term.

Use Case III: *Bike sharing*

In assessing the impact of the FCs on equity with respect to Bike sharing, the results suggest that women are particularly concerned about accessibility, safety, awareness and cost. The challenges of women could be understood in the context of the availability and accessibility of the services and the safety of the bicycle infrastructure with respect to shared vehicular/bicycle network and traffic speed. Policy and interventions should focus on ensuring bikes availability at stations, the reliability of the services and providing safe infrastructure. The key FCs with the potential to deliver equity for women as users of bicycle-sharing services are FCs "FC237: Provide recommendations to customers with alternative routes avoiding high-speed roads from point A to B, "FC312: Separate cycle lanes free from vehicular traffic" and "FC332: Safe cycle routes for cycling with children" are the highest rank FCs in the achieving equity in the se of bike-sharing. The finding of this use case can be easily used in fields like scooter sharing and similar services of sharing.

Use Case IV: *Employability in the transport sector*

In assessing the impact of the FCs on equity with respect to women employability in the transport sector, the results suggest that women are particularly concerned about career development and flexible working opportunities. These challenges should be understood in the context women needs relating to the family and childcare responsibilities that most career

women also deal with. The key FCs with the potential to deliver equity for women employability in the transport sector are the measure that relates to CSR protocol readiness “FC451: To have ready a written CSR protocol / policy” and FC313: Ability of staff to change shift patterns at short notice to reflect caring needs”.

Similarly, the results show that 82% of FCs remained the in the top 10 FCs of Vertex 3 of the Inclusion Diamond (employment Today) and 85% for Vertex 6 (employment tomorrow, under the futuristic scenario of employment based on logistics of drones). These indicate that less than 20% of the top 10 FCs changed from the analysis in both vertexes. Hence, the Top 10 FCs of UC IV are sustainable in the long-term.

40% of Top 10 FCs for POLISH and SPANISH women are different in the UC IV, we however, do not have any resource to explain the observed difference.

The findings of UC IV (employment of women in jobs related with the transport system) can be easily used in fields like motor vehicle drivers, building frame and related trade workers, managers of small enterprises, construction, physical and engineering science technicians and machinery mechanics.

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Terminology and Acronyms

AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
AV	Autonomous Vehicle
BN	Bayesian Network
CFC	Cluster of Fairness Characteristics
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DM	Decision Maker
3Es	Efficiency, effectiveness, equity
EU	European Union
FC	Fairness Characteristics
FM	Fairness Measures
GRI	Global Reporting Initiative
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HR	Human Resources
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
PE	Production Equity
PI	Polyhedral Individual
MCDM	Multi-criteria decision making
SA	Sensitivity Analysis
SO	Specific Objective
SQAS	Safety & Quality Assessment for Sustainability
UC	Use Case
UN	United Nations

I. Introduction

In general, impact assessment can be described as a stepwise procedure with the objective of establishing the social benefits of a project and the extent to which the identified indicators address the sub-objectives and the overall objective of the project. The DIAMOND project is intended to provide a tool for influencing future transport policy and infrastructure development towards achieving fair inclusion for women in four thematic areas (defined in ‘Deliverable D2.1 Use Case Definition’) (DIAMOND Project, 2020) in the transportation sector.

This deliverable builds on D7.1, D7.2, (DIAMOND Project 2019b, 2020b) the data collected in Work Package 3, the analysis in Work Package 4 and works in Work Packages 5 and 6. To assess the impact of DIAMOND project’s fairness characteristics in addressing fair inclusion for women in transport systems. Deliverable D7.3 “Final impact assessment” is tasked with the development of a common monitoring framework to assess the level of impact of the project results (Fairness measures) in addressing social justice and fairness in the transport systems and to demonstrate the extent to which each proposed fairness measure will contribute to fair women inclusion in the transport sector. These objectives are directly linked to the main problems identified in the use-cases and focussed on assessing the impact of DIAMOND in the four thematic areas.

In this section we consider the definition of fairness as operationalized in the DIAMOND project and the working definition of women which is based on gender (DIAMOND Project, 2019, 2019a, 2021a). Section 2 presents the methodology section with the framework for the impact assessment and the productive equity analysis. In Section 3, the four use cases are discussed and the key factors effecting women’s travel choices and factor influencing the career choices of women in the transport sector extracted from the data are presented in the form of Fairness characteristics (FCs). Section 4 presents the Productive Equity Analysis (3Es). In Section 5, the results of the sensitivity and sustainability analysis (sustainability assessment) are presented. Section 6 describes the results of the replicability assessment. Section 7 presents the assessment of potential certifications and standardization and Section 8 presents the concluding remarks.

I.1 Fairness and Equity in the Transport Sector

Fairness can be a vague and somewhat ambiguous concept which can evolve and change over time and space and can be based on individual subjective reasoning and experiences. This makes any attempt at producing a universal definition a difficult process. The terms “fairness” and “justice” tend to be used to describe both how decisions are made and how individuals are treated within a community. Throughout the wider literature the notion of fairness is closely related to the concepts of **justice, equity, and human rights**. Hence fairness needs to reflect access or opportunity to use the transport system, but also the distribution of benefits across the transport system.

The DIAMOND project defines fair transportation system as a transport system that provides “fair and equal opportunity for people with a variety of different characteristics to access a safe, secure, effective and efficient transport system that meet their daily needs”. This definition is consistent with the definition found in Martens (2017).

Equity in transport and accessibility has been discussed in several dimensions. Lee et al (2017) introduced five dimensions related specifically to fairness with regards to public use of and access to public transport.

- **Social equity:** refers to the distribution of impacts by population segments that differ in abilities and needs, for example, income, age, gender, or ability to travel
- **Spatial equity:** is a geographical level of analysis which looks to examine where the inequality is taking place, this is important in relation to transport policy planning “because the effects of public policies tend to cluster around specific physical locations” (p. 213)
- **Procedural equity:** – is associated with equity in the policy making process as opposed to the outcome of policy, in the case of transport policy planning procedural equity is related to having fair and equal evaluations included in the policy making decision.
- **Modal equity:** is related to ensuring that there is safe access for all groups to the range of local transport modes, the example provided is that “because walking and bicycling have higher mortality rates from vehicle accidents than driving, modal equity strategies would seek to restrict driving in order to slow or reduce vehicle traffic” (p. 215)¹
- **Distribution equity:** is linked to how transportation costs and benefits are distributed across society, currently this is evaluated for fairness by examining the accessibility to transport infrastructures which excludes any evaluation of how safely and easily people can travel to the station.

From this perspective inequitable or unfair transport policies and planning can have diverse and significant impacts on various groups at various times in relation to individuals’ economic and social opportunities (DIAMOND Project 2019). Although the focus of this project is fair access for women, ‘fairness’ applies to all people, but certain types of unfairness disproportionately affect people with certain characteristics, in particular, women (or groups such as women with young children). The achievement of the objectives of DIAMOND is dependent on the improvement of transport systems in four selected use-cases (e.g., Public transport and infrastructure, Vehicles with dynamic control, Vehicle (bike) sharing and Employment of women in the transport industry) based on equity-efficiency-effectiveness criteria.

A working **definition of fairness** for the DIAMOND project is: a state in which people are treated similarly, unimpeded by prejudices or unnecessary distinctions or barriers, except they can be explicitly justified (D4.2).

¹ This can be extended to considering the effects of using modes (e.g. the consequences of accidents at different speeds on pedestrians) and which may disproportionately affect certain groups (e.g. children). It is partly the basis for introducing lower speed limits (e.g. around 30km/h) in many cities, such as Edinburgh in Scotland.

2. METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

The impact assessment is divided in 2 parts (refer to Section 7 of D2.2):

- ◆ **Productive Equity assessment:** Where the Equity, Effectiveness and Efficiency (3Es) key performance indicators (KPIs) will be identified and measured on a regular basis per each Use Case. This measurement of the Equity KPIs will be done through SIMULATION by applying Bayesian Networks.
- ◆ **Sensitivity analysis:** This sensitivity analysis is again divided in two parts:
 - *Sensitivity analysis of results over time:* Where we analyse how robust are our results in the mid and long term.
 - *Sensitivity analysis of results over space:* Where we analyse how robust are our results in through different cultures around Europe (basically East: Spain and West: Poland).

Although we have focussed on the profile “Women as a homogeneous group”, our algorithms and toolbox are able to address whatever profile is selected by the user of the Diamond Toolbox and the Diamond methodology.

2.1 Productive Equity assessment-3Es

The 3Es methodology defines KPIs for effectiveness, efficiency and equity. These KPIs are based on ratios benefit/cost. Regarding quantifying these benefits based on real observations. Since the 3Es cannot be obtained in the project life, simulation based on Bayesian Network (BN) analysis is applied to estimate these ratios on the expectations and feelings of women (refer to section 5.3 “Simulation system for impact assessment” of D2.2).

Figure 1: Productive equity analysis

For each use case it was obtained a list of the top 10 FCs combining the results of the analytical hierarchical process (for level 1 and 2 FCs) and Bayesian networks (for level 3 FCs) (DIAMOND Project, 2021), and to each of these top 10 FCs it has been defined which (fairness) measures can be applied to improve the fairness and the women satisfaction as users or employees. Bayesian networks allowed us to build a model or directed acyclic graph that establishes the interrelations between variables and allows us to, through inferences, evaluate how a change in one variable (e.g. an answer to a survey, observation value, etc.) would influence in the others.

2.1.1 Simulation through Inferences to Make Predictions

Transport service providers and employers could be interested in improving these most relevant factors to increase fairness in their organizations and in knowing how these improvements are affecting other factors (level 3 FCs). BNs were used to simulate by inferences the impact of a change in a BN variable on the others.

Inferences for each UC were made by sampling with the Bayesian model that best fit the data (Mazzocchi, 2008; Gauthier and Hawley, 2015); the best model was determined by calculating the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) of each network (Akaike, 1974) (see Equation (4) and Figure I in the Annex II).

$$AIC = 2k - 2\ln(L) \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), k is the number of BN variables in the model and L is the maximum likelihood function, which measures the goodness of fit of the BN model to a sample of data of the variables. It is formed from the joint probability distribution of the sample, but viewed and used only as a function of the parameters, thus treating the random variables as fixed at the observed values (Akaike, 1974).

After selecting the Bayesian model with the lowest AIC, the development of the simulations allowed us to analyze how the implementation of a Fairness Measure or recommendation through changes in the associated BN variable (e.g., instantiating the selected BN variable with the best score) influence on probabilities of the values of the other top 10 FCs by the users or employees and then on their satisfaction (Molero *et al.*, 2021). The code used to develop these simulations is shown in Figure 2 in Annex II.

These simulations allow us the calculation of 3Es KPIs as explained in the following section.

2.1.2. 3Es calculation

A. Calculation of the Effectiveness KPI

As it is already explained in D7.1 and D7.2 (DIAMOND Project 2019b, 2020b), effectiveness represents the ratio of actual outputs (impacts generated by proposed measures and the a priori determined objectives). Since the main objective is to improve satisfaction of the participants in transport system (in different subcategories – as passengers, as users of autonomous vehicles or public bike system or as employees).

Bayesian networks generate a more comprehensive estimation of effectiveness – contribution of specific fairness measure to the overall goal includes also its contribution to other fairness measures which are also necessary for fulfilling the overall goal of a specific use case.

To obtain the EFFECTIVENESS of one Fairness Measure or recommendation, we focus on how the implementation of a Fairness measure to improve one of the Top 10 FCs influences in the probabilities of the possible satisfaction scores of the other nine Top 10 FCs for a specific profile. After instantiating the value of one BN variable associated to the FC, we obtain the probabilities of the other 9 top10 FCs variables before and after doing the investment in implementing the fairness measure, defining the EFFECTIVENESS indicator as the addition of the differences between these 2 probabilities for all these 9 Top10 FCs:

After Instantiating the value of FC=1 to the maximum satisfaction score thanks to the implementation of a Fairness Measure (FM) or recommendation:

B. Calculation of the Equity KPI

The EQUITY indicator is obtained as the ratio between the Effectiveness KPI for a specific profile of women and the same specific profile of men (For instance: Women with disabilities living in rural areas vs. Men with disabilities living in rural areas)

Hence, the formula for the EQUITY KPI is given below:

$$EQUITY\ KPI = \frac{EFFECTIVENESS\ KPI_{WOMEN}}{EFFECTIVENESS\ KPI_{MEN}}$$

The next picture will clarify a bit more the concept:

PROFILE: WOMEN as a homogeneous Group			A	B	EQUITY INDICATOR
			ΣΔ Women	ΣΔ Men	A/B
	Top10 Factors about inclusion	Associated Recommendation			
FC321	Offering adequate personal space	Staff present to provide real-time assistance to people who need assistance	1.1	1.3	0.9
FC322	Improved ventilation and air-conditioning	Improve cross-ventilation and air-conditioned environments suitable for different seasons	1.4	1.1	1.2
FC111	Walking time from the points of interest to the public transport access points	Availability of information that indicate and allows access to key destination	0.8	0.5	1.5

Figure 3: Equity KPI Calculation

EQUITY ratios higher than 1 indicate that the implementation of a Fairness Measure (recommendation) improves the satisfaction of women more than to satisfaction of men. In contrary, a equity ratio lower than 1 leads to unsatisfactory results. Therefore, fairness measures are more preferable that generate higher equity ratio. However, since the aim is to achieve equity, we prefer the EQUITY ratio which is closer to 1, in order to improve the satisfaction of women without sacrificing too much the satisfaction of men.

C. Calculation of the Efficiency KPI

EFFICIENCY represents the ratio between produced outputs and required inputs. Since the produced outputs in this specific application correspond to the value of effectiveness, efficiency can be estimated as the ratio between effectiveness and the total costs of a specific fairness measure.

Since it is assumed that all Fairness Measures represent point-input continuous-output investments, the cost is calculated by applying a capital recovery factor (A/P, i%,n) where P is present value of an investment in a fairness measure, A is equivalent annual value obtained for a constant interest rate i=5% and respective economic life of investment n.

So the formula for the EFFICIENCY indicator is the next:

$$EFFICIENCY\ KPI = \frac{Effectiveness\ KPI}{COST\ of\ implementing\ the\ FM}$$

The next picture will clarify better this concept:

PROFILE: WOMEN as a homogeneous Group			A	B	EQUITY INDICATOR	EFFECTIVENESS INDICATOR	COST (€/YEAR)	EFFICIENCY
			$\sum \Delta$ Women	$\sum \Delta$ Men	A/B	A	G(€)	A/G
	Top10 Factors about inclusion	Associated Recommendation						
FC321	Offering adequate personal space	Staff present to provide real-time assistance to people who need assistance	1.1	1.3	0.9	1.1	57600	1.9
FC322	Improved ventilation and air-conditioning	Improve cross-ventilation and air-conditioned environments suitable for different seasons	1.4	1.1	1.2	1.4	6168	22.1

Figure 4: Efficiency KPI Calculation

2.2 Sensitivity and sustainability analysis methodology

A. Methodology to assess the Sustainability of results over the time

Sensitivity and sustainability analysis is carried out to assess the sensitivity and sustainability of DIAMOND's results over a period of time. In a multi-criteria decision making (MCDM), the selection and prioritisation (assigning weights) of criteria is essential. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) provides a mathematical framework for this purpose when analysing complex decision problems (Saaty, 1987). The AHP derives the weights through pairwise comparisons of the relative importance between each two criteria. Through a pairwise comparison matrix, the AHP utilises a decision-making technique involving numerical analysis of a set of discrete alternatives to calculate the weight value for each criterion (w_i) by taking the eigenvector corresponding to the largest eigenvalue of the matrix, and then normalising the sum of the components to unity (Saaty, 1987; Saaty and Vargas, 2013). This process is achieved through the following steps (Triantaphyllou and Sánchez, 1997);

- ◆ Determine the relevant FCs and sub-levels.
- ◆ Attach numerical measures to the relative importance (i.e., weights) of the FCs.
- ◆ Process the numerical values to determine a ranking FCs for each Use Case.

The AHP Sensitivity Analysis (AHP-SA) framework provides a means for investigating the sensitivity of criteria weights by altering criterion weight values calculated by the AHP in percentage increments and decrements.

The AHP-SA framework offers decision makers a simple but robust tool for exploring the sensitivity of criteria weights output from the AHP analysis on the MCDM results. It enables the evaluation of the sensitivity of MCDM criteria to weight changes.

The weights obtained in the AHP-SA (level global weights obtained as the multiplication of level 1 local weights by level two local weights) are multiplied by the corresponding level 3 FCs weights obtained through Bayesian networks analysis.

In this way we can analyse how robust are the results (Top10 FCs) in different scenarios (present and future) in the mid and long term or in different cultures, because this evolution in the time or in the space is simulated through these variations in the weights of the preferences in the level 1 (Poveda-Reyes et al., 2021):

Figure 5: AHP Sensitivity Analysis

B. Methodology to assess the Sustainability of results over the Space

In this case, the method that has been used to assess the robustness of the results when cultures are changed is to compare the weights of level 3 TOP 10 FCs for POLAND (East of Europe) and for SPAIN (West of Europe).

A comparison analysis between standard levels by using an ANOVA analysis has also been conducted in order to explain the significant differences in the TOP 10 FCs between POLAND and SPAIN.

2.3 Replicability to other transport context

The current project is based only on four use cases, and the findings may or may not be applied in other transport context. Therefore, the DIAMOND Project assesses the impact of the outputs in fields like aviation, logistic or maritime transport, which are outside the scope of the DIAMOND Project. Additionally, considering the focuses on fairness with regard to women, we also investigate the transferability of the results from women to men and its impact.

Section 6 of this report presents the detailed discussions on this section.

2.4 Impacts on certification and standards

There is a high possibility that the results from the DIAMOND Project may have implication for certification policies regarding women and fairness. We investigate and present the impact of the new measures and policies identified and tested in the project on the certification process and propose a review or upgrade of national and EU standards accordingly.

3. Use Case Definition and Fairness Measures

The research applied a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative research methods, comprising a comprehensive literature review, DAD surveys, online surveys, interviews, user satisfaction surveys and focus group discussions (Gorrini *et al.*, 2019; García-jiménez *et al.*, 2020). The list of the most relevant Fairness Characteristics (FCs) or women needs was obtained from the quantitative data analysis (AHP and machine learning techniques) and from the qualitative data analysis (through the interdisciplinary analysis, Focus groups and semi-structured interviews). The most relevant Fairness Characteristics (FCs) were weighted and hierarchized using the AHP (Poveda-Reyes *et al.*, 2021) and Bayesian Network analysis (Molero *et al.*, 2021).

After determining the main needs and barriers women (as a homogeneous group) face, an ANOVA analysis was carried out to in the Top 10 FCs per each use case for this specific profile (Women as a homogeneous group, what means that we only instantiate the socio-demographic characteristic “Gender”). The aim was to define if there are significant differences for the characteristics/profiles of the polyhedral individual (PI) and also set which specific profiles were the lowest satisfied according to the UESI responses.

Finally, the recommendations were set. To do so, an interdisciplinary panel made of experts provided the recommendations:

1. The recommendations generated for **Top 10 FCs** for the profile “Women as a homogeneous group” for all the UCs took into consideration the ANOVA analysis by addressing the **specific women profiles most unsatisfied**. Moreover, experts’ attendees to a specific **workshop validate them** (16 attendees to UC-I session, 13 attendees to UC-II session, 9 attendees to UC-III session and 8 attendees to UC-IV session).
2. The recommendations generated for **the rest of FCs** were **validated through an online survey**. A FM was considered validated if at least the 80% of the respondents considered appropriate the recommendation and more than 5 respondents participated in the survey.

The following sections describe the four use-cases and their respective key FCs (e.g., UCI: Public transport and infrastructure, UCII: autonomous vehicles, UCIII: Vehicle (bike) sharing and UCIV: Employment of women in the transport industry).

3.1 Use case I: Public transport and infrastructures. Railways.

3.1.1 Use Case I definition

It is claimed that current transport systems do not always take gendered differences into account when either developing or delivering services. The objective of Use Case I is to investigate women’s needs as users of **metro and urban railway public transport**. This is aimed at supporting the development of gender-equitable transport planning policies. The use-case goal is to increase the percentage of women using public transport during peak and off-peak hours.

The **Inclusion Diamond** representation for the Use Case I is based on the following vertexes:

- ◆ Vertex VI - Transport infrastructure and business model today;

- Layer L3 - Public transport;
- ◆ Vertex V4 - Transport infrastructure and business models tomorrow;
 - Layer L1 - New technologies;
 - Layer L2 - New business models.

3.1.2 Fairness characteristics (FCs) and Fairness Measures for UC I

The Top 10 Fairness Characteristics (FCs) for the profile “Women as a homogeneous group” and their associated Fairness Measures (FMs) identified from the analysis of the data collected for the UC I are shown below:

Table I: UC I: Identified Fairness Characteristics and their validated Fairness Measures

Fairness Characteristics				Fairness Measure
Code	Level 1 FC	Level 2 FC	Level 3 FC	
FC111	Accessibility	service and availability	Walking time from the points of interest to the public transport access points	Availability of information that indicate and allows access to key destination
FC112			Reliability of the service modes available	Coordinated timetables between the different transport modes in the stations.
FC114			Level of service at the public transport access point	Adapt the station access with ramps, escalators and lifts for users with special needs.
FC115			Number of service available within the transport infrastructure	Display the next services in the station.
FC116			Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, alternative shared mobility service,	Adapted connection paths and access points to all users (including people with reduced mobility, women with children...)
FC315	Safety and security	Harassment	Visibility of the surrounding area of the station	Increase lightning in the stations and their surroundings
FC316			Complaint information point in case of violations to personal safety	Improve response time of security staff
FC318			Display advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicizing helpline numbers	Train the people attending the help line on equality and gender.
FC321		overcrowding	Offering adequate personal space	Staff present to provide real-time assistance to people who need assistance
FC322			Improved ventilation and air-conditioning	Improve cross-ventilation and air-conditioned environments suitable for different seasons
FC323			Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating)	Improve seating design that fulfils the need and/or with appropriation given to pregnant women, persons/carers with toddlers, disabled persons, etc.

3.2 Use case II: Autonomous Vehicles

3.2.1 Use Case II definition

Many of the existing private vehicles women drive are modelled on the general physicality of men, which creates issues with regards to seating, posture and the seatbelt safety. AV technology is still emerging and may use algorithms based on databases which reflect past biases in car use rather than fairness across the potential population of users (for a full view of discussion see Deliverable 2.2 of DIAMOND) (DIAMOND Project, 2019).

The objective of the Use Case II is to investigate women’s emotional needs as passengers of autonomous vehicles. The goal of the Use Case II is to increase the level of acceptance of women towards autonomous driving technology and identify what the key factors are that affect women’s travel choices for design consideration.

The **Inclusion Diamond** representation for the Use Case II is based on:

- ◆ Vertex V2 - Vehicle today;
 - Layer LI - Public transport
- ◆ Vertex V5 - Vehicles tomorrow;
 - Layer LI – Road Transport

3.2.2 Fairness characteristics (FCs) and Fairness Measures for UC II

The Top 10 Fairness Characteristics (FCs) for the profile “Women as a homogeneous group” and their associated Fairness Measures (FMs) identified from the analysis of the data collected for the UC II are shown below:

Table 2: UCII: Identified Fairness Characteristics and their validated Fairness Measures

Fairness Characteristics				Fairness Measure
FC Code	Level 1 FC	Level 2 FC	Level 3 FC	
FC219	Comfort	trust in technology	Trust in technology in the case of bad weather	Dissemination and promotional campaigns about safety mechanisms in the case of bad weather.
FC223		Simultaneity	Perception of the degree of interaction between passengers	Possibility to choose the degree of interaction/private space (included in the last version of maturity mode)
FC224			Driving when performing simultaneous tasks in comfortable external environment	Comfortably perform non-driving related tasks such as work: sitting, postures, auxiliary surfaces, electronic facilities and be easily reconfigurable
FC228			Perception of boredom	The interior vehicle design facilitates the execution of non-driving related tasks.
FC229			Perception of joy	Include the possibility of a relax atmosphere (lighting condition, thermal comfort, music...)
FC521	Environment	emissions	Perception of reduction of ecological impact	Ecological impact evaluated and communicated to passengers by proper

Fairness Characteristics				Fairness Measure
FC Code	Level 1 FC	Level 2 FC	Level 3 FC	
				indicators during the use of AV on regular basis assessment
FC531		public health	Perception of public health when driving without steering wheel	Promotion campaigns for public awareness about benefits of automated driving versus manual/conventional cars
FC6319	Design	vehicle behaviour	Importance of optimising well-being of other road users to determine vehicle behaviour	Education on the social benefits of the various driving parameters for users to make informed decisions when selecting the automatic driving parameter
FC6327			Importance on controlling speed	Automated system for speed controlling
FC637			Vehicle behaviour under sportive driving	Education about sportive driving mode when it is activated: Benefits and disadvantages

3.3 Use case III: Bike-sharing services

3.3.1 Use Case III definition

Literature on women mobility suggests that women make several shorter and multi-purpose trips involving multi-stop (trip-chaining) than men. Women are more likely to be responsible for domestic chores, childcare, shopping and children school trips (Duchène, 2011; Ancaes, 2012; Lam, 2016; Gauvin *et al.*, 2019). Most of these trips are either too far to walk or too close and complex, thus making the use of public transportation time consuming and inconvenient (Monisha *et al.*, 2019). However, it is evident that women cycle less or use bicycle-sharing services less than men (Howland *et al.*, 2017; McNeil *et al.*, 2017, 2018). The objective of the Use Case III is therefore to investigate women's needs and barriers faced as users of bike sharing services in Europe. The goal of the Use Case III is to increase the percentage of women using bike sharing services.

The **Inclusion Diamond** representation for the Use Case III is based on:

- ◆ Vertex VI - Transport infrastructure and business model today;
 - Layer L3 - Public transport;
- ◆ Vertex V4 - Transport infrastructure and business models tomorrow;
 - Layer L1 - New technologies;
 - Layer L2 - New business models.

3.3.2 Fairness characteristics (FCs) and Fairness Measures for UC III

The Top 10 Fairness Characteristics (FCs) for the profile “Women as a homogeneous group” and their associated Fairness Measures (FMs) identified from the analysis of the data collected for the UC III are shown below:

Table 3: UCIII: Identified Fairness Characteristics and their validated Fairness Measures

Fairness Characteristics				Fairness Measure
Code	Level 1 FC	Level 2 FC	Level 3 FC	
FC114	Accessibility and Spontaneity	Membership cost	Safety equipment provided including helmets, hi-vis vest, rain ponchos	Ensure that all bikes have well-functioning safety lights and brakes
FC132		Proximity of docking station	Available to those in low-income neighbourhoods	Implement plans to establish stations in low-income communities trying to make them available within 400m radius in these communities.
FC144		Inadequate infrastructure	Attractive changing facilities	Genderized changing rooms with required commodities for women.
FC237	Safety and Security	Personal safety	Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes	Provide recommendations to customers with alternative routes avoiding high speed roads from point A to B.
FC312	Social constraints	Socio-cultural constraints	Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling	Separate cycle lanes free from vehicular traffic
FC322			Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling	More inclusive promotional campaigns including disability persons.
FC332		Family responsibility	Safe cycle routes for cycling with children	Lobby local authority for safe routes to school etc. and publicly monitoring progress.
FC333			Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo.	Provide accessories to facilitate traveling with children or shopping (child seat or basket)
FC412	Weather and Topography	Topography	Avoid hilly terrain in the development of cycle networks where possible.	Offer electric bikes to customers
FC421		Weather	All weather cycle-friendly infrastructure	The cycling lanes should be prepared for rainy days in terms of friction, etc.

3.4 Use case IV: Employment

3.4.1 Use Case VI definition

Use Case IV is linked to the employment of women in jobs related with the transport system. The objective of the Use Case IV is to investigate women’s needs as employees in the transport sector, and specifically to consider the key factors regarding fairness and inclusiveness of employment for women across the transport sector and help to increase the percentage of women working on-site and off-site in the railway, freight transport and the logistics sectors.

The **Inclusion Diamond** representation for the Use Case IV is based on:

- ◆ Vertex V3 – Polyhedral Individual as job holder today;
 - Layer L4 – On-site professional jobs
 - Layer L5 – Off-site professional jobs
- ◆ Vertex V6 - Polyhedral Individual as job holder tomorrow;
 - Layer L4 – On-site professional jobs
 - Layer L5 – Off-site professional jobs

3.4.2 Fairness characteristics (FCs) and Fairness Measures for UC IV

The Top 10 Fairness Characteristics (FCs) for the profile “Women as a homogeneous group” and their associated Fairness Measures (FMs) identified from the analysis of the data collected for the UC IV are shown below:

Table 4: UCIV: Identified Fairness Characteristics and their validated Fairness Measures

Fairness Characteristics				Fairness Measure
FC Code	Level 1 FC	Level 2 FC	Level 3 FC	
FC313	Personal Circumstances	Caring/Parenting responsibilities	Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time; (Opportunity for flexible working)	Ability of staff to change shift patterns at short notice to reflect caring needs
FC133			Family friendly working conditions for different categories of workers (e.g. professions that require prolonged absence from home)	Allow flexible part-time working arrangements like reduced working hours or home office provisions
FC123	Socio-economic Conditions	Demand Factors	Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed (Recruitment - Written and formal Recruitment polices (that cannot be altered by frontline managers))	Use a wide range of media platforms for adverts to ensure wider spread
FC214		Policy/Legal	Integrate the company’s commitment to gender equality into all of its communication activities and HR policies;	Gender neutral employment advertisement

Fairness Characteristics				Fairness Measure
FC Code	Level 1 FC	Level 2 FC	Level 3 FC	
FC255	Job Characteristics	Safety and security	Security staff available to intervene in case of need. (Additional safety process are in place for lone working/night time working)	Ensure security and police support can be accessed rapidly by staff.
FC252			Applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment;	Organize training sessions for all the staff
FC451		Training Provision	Diversity training in general and specifically for ethnicity	To have ready a written CSR protocol / policy
FC132			Equal employment policies: Policies are used within the organisation to support fair recruitment and promotion processes for women, and meet national legal requirements (including Equal Employment policies);	Equal access for all employees to training and development opportunities for general upskilling, transferring roles flexibility of training delivery
FC115		Terms and Conditions	Ensuring gender pay equality for equivalent positions;	Flexibility against maternity to avoid glass ceilings in the professional development process of women.
FC215		HR Policies	Ensure that the male–female ratio of internal promotions in different job categories is in line with the average male–female ratio of the company staff;	Equity plans going beyond legal statements

4. Productive Equity Analysis for the profile “Women as a homogeneous group”

Equity in transport and accessibility can be discussed in several dimensions including vertical equity, horizontal equity, social equity (Geurs, Dentinho and Patuelli, 2016). Vertical equity describes the extent to which members of different classes are treated equally. Horizontal equity defines the extent to which individuals within the same social class (such as income, gender, ability, and ethnicity) are treated similarly. While social equity refers to the distribution of impacts by population segments that differ in abilities and needs, for example, income, age, gender, or ability to travel (Geurs, Dentinho and Patuelli, 2016). Transport equity can thus be viewed as the distribution of a minimum required level of accessibility based on principles of social justice and fairness (Martens, 2017; Brussel et al., 2019). Therefore, the distribution of transport as a social good should be guided by the benefits and not cost associated costs and externalities (Martens, 2012).

According to DIAMOND's definition of fair transport systems (DIAMOND Project, 2019), social equity or equity in transport would mean that everyone should enjoy a safe, secure, effective, and efficient transport system, even when people with special needs require extra resources and subsidies. The achievement of the objectives of DIAMOND is dependent on the improvement of transport systems in the selected four use-cases (e.g., Public transport and infrastructure, Vehicles with dynamic control, Vehicle (bike) sharing and Employment of women in the transport industry) based on equity-efficiency-effectiveness criteria.

For these reasons, DIAMOND performs equity analysis as part of the cost-benefit analysis (equity-efficiency-effectiveness analysis). From the perspective of DIAMOND, the primary purpose of the fairness characteristics or measures is the improvement of women’s mobility and employment in the transport sector, in other words, accessibility improvements. The Concept of equity-efficiency-effectiveness analysis is discussed below.

4.1 Effectiveness, Efficiency and Equity (3Es) for “Women as a homogeneous group”

Given that it is impossible to address all the fairness characteristics of groups of women for all the Use Cases, the framework equity-efficiency-effectiveness or 3Es approach as a three-dimensional simultaneous planning system for allocating resources for public services provision, will be utilised. We use this framework of effectiveness, efficiency, and equity to provide a tool for deciding which fairness measures to implement and at which points in time. Therefore, we evaluate the fairness measures through the lens of effectiveness to determine if they result in significant achievement of the project objectives. An efficiency perspective determines whether the fairness measures make the best use of resources. Finally, an equity focus can determine if resources are distributed across groups fairly (Aday et al. 2004). The following discussion highlights the application of the effectiveness, efficiency, and equity criteria in this study. Tables 5-8 provide numerical outputs of the 3Es computation for all UCs as well as the description of the fairness measures in terms of investment costs. Tables 5 – UCI, Table 6 – UCII, Table 7 – UCIII and Table 8 – UCIV.

Use Case I: Public Transport - Railways

Table 5: UCI 3Es Indicators for the profile “Women as a homogeneous group”

LEVEL 3 FAIRNESS CHARACTERISTICS		FAIRNESS MEASURES	3Es KPI					COST DESCRIPTION
			EFFECTIVENESS INDICATOR		EQUITY INDICATOR	COST (€/YEAR)	EFFICIENCY INDICATOR	
			Women (A)	Men (B)	A/B	G	A/G	
FC114	Level of service at the public transport access point	Adapt the station access with ramps, escalators and lifts for users with special needs.	1.5	0.4	3.4	4610	32.0	Capital costs included for 5 wheelchair ramps and 5 handicap lifts, Economic life: 10 years
FC115	Number of service available within the transport infrastructure	Display the next services in the station.	1.6	1.1	1.5	121	1309.5	This FM must be line-based on-ground and on-board, not possible to implement it only in one station. The cost is estimated based on recent example from Polish railways: The system includes 101 dynamic passenger information boards, INFO/SOS communication, and 86 video-monitoring cameras - 1.26 Mil EUR. Interest rate: 5%, economic life is different for different component, it is assumed 15 years.
FC321	Offering adequate personal space	Staff present to provide real-time assistance to people who need assistance	1.1	1.3	0.9	57600	1.9	Gross cost per employee per year is 28800. Two employees are included
FC322	Improved ventilation and air-conditioning	Improve cross-ventilation and air-conditioned environments suitable for different seasons	1.4	1.1	1.2	6168	22.1	For 500 sqm, the following cost components are included: capital cost, maintenance cost and energy cost, Economic life: 15 years.
FC111	Walking time from the points of interest to the public transport access points	Availability of information that indicate and allows access to key destination points	0.8	0.5	1.5	3560	22.7	5 digital signage screens (one costs 712 EUR per annum); Economic life: 12 years.
FC116	Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, alternative shared mobility service.	Adapted connection paths and access points to all users (including people with reduced mobility, women with children...)	0.5	0.6	0.9	16803	3.2	Following assumptions are included in the estimation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stopping points for other connecting modes of transport within the station (one bus stop); Economic life: 20 years • Car park (30 spaces) Economic life: 20 years • Accessible entrances and exits (five + five related to FM10) • Five information boards Economic life: 5 years

Table 5: UCI 3Es Indicators- Continuation

LEVEL 3 FAIRNESS CHARACTERISTICS		FAIRNESS MEASURES	3Es KPI					COST DESCRIPTION
			EFFECTIVENESS INDICATOR		EQUITY INDICATOR	COST (€/YEAR)	EFFICIENCY INDICATOR	
			Women (A)	Men (B)	A/B	G	A/G	
FC316	Complaint information point in case of violations to personal safety	Improve response time of security staff	1.1	0.9	1.2	1190	89.5	Security Operations Centre: 12 employees + 24x7 active Security Operations Centre
FC315	Visibility of the surrounding area of the station	Increase lightning in the stations and their surroundings	0.5	1.1	0.5	1361	40.1	In stations: 500 sqm, 165 led bulbs needed, installation 5 EUR per bulb, life: 3 years, interest rate: 5%; Access roads: 500 sqm (100 m x 5 m of width): 0.35 EUR/sqm + energy consumption for internal leg lights (9.63 kWh per annum)
FC112	Reliability of the service modes available	Coordinated timetables between the different transport modes in the stations.	0.8	0.4	1.7	9393	8.1	Fixed schedule rail service; optimizing the schedules of bus services; Total cost (operating + passenger waiting cost + transfer cost) decreases due to the decrease of passenger waiting and transfer cost). Here only operating costs are included since they have a positive direction (increase). Input parameters: Unit bus operating cost: 212.5 EUR/km (average cost for London area) Average round trip time for a set of 10 routes: 60 min; Average headway for non-coordinated scenario is 15 min, for coordinated scenario is 13 min, This makes operating cost increase 1089.7 per hour and capital cost increase (additional buses needed) of 2233440 - this is a scenario if you need to buy the buses (other option is reallocation or leasing). Additional bus fleet needed for coordinated scenario: 110 buses (price of a bus is 180k EUR and economic life 12 years, interest rate: 5%)
FC318	Display advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicizing helpline numbers	Train the people attending the help line on equality and gender.	0.0	1.2	0.0	1800	0.0	Total number of attendees: 100; 4 groups per 25; 2 rounds. In total: 4*2 = 8 sessions, each session 60 minutes; Price of trainee per session: 200 EUR In total 1600 EUR + training material (200 EUR) = 1800 EUR
FC323	Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating)	Improve seating design that fulfils the need and/or with appropriation given to pregnant women, persons/carers with toddlers, disabled persons, etc.	0.0	0.0	0.0	613	0.0	Waiting room in station: 4732 EUR for 100 sqm for 40 places with 8 places for persons with wheelchairs or toddlers. Waiting room on platform (with glass walls and 4-side entrances): 46298.4 EUR. Distributed over a life of 10 years with interest rate of i=5% that is: 612.79 and 5995.6 per year, respectively.

Use Case II: Autonomous vehicles

Table 6: UCII 3Es Indicators for the profile “Women as a homogeneous group”

LEVEL 3 FAIRNESS CHARACTERISTICS		FAIRNESS MEASURES	3Es KPI					COST DESCRIPTION (All costs are distributed on a 5 year life of a car with interest rate 5%)
			EFFECTIVENESS INDICATOR		EQUITY INDICATOR	COST (€/YEAR)	EFFICIENCY INDICATOR	
			Women (A)	Men (B)	A/B	G	A/G	
FC228	Perception of boredom	The interior vehicle design facilitates the execution of non-driving related tasks.	0.1	0.1	1.1	693	15.1894661	Estimation based on costs needed for Tesla cars: 3500\$ or 3000 EUR.
FC229	Perception of joy	Include the possibility of a relax atmosphere (lighting condition, thermal comfort, music...)	0.0	0.0	0.0	693	0	The part of infotainment system
FC223	Perception of the degree of interaction between passengers	Possibility to choose the degree of interaction/private space (included in the last version of maturity mode)	0.5	0.2	2.7	350	146.051314	Based on expert opinions.
FC521	Perception of reduction of ecological impact	Ecological impact evaluated and communicated to passengers by proper indicators during the use of AV on regular basis assessment	0.0	0.0	0.0	23.1	0	CO2 sensor with display costs 100 EUR
FC6327	Importance on controlling speed	Automated system for speed controlling	0.6	0.1	9.2	46.2	1223.45801	ACC costs around 200 EUR/car. Economic life: 5 years.
FC224	Driving when performing simultaneous tasks in comfortable external environment	Comfortably perform non-driving related tasks such as work: sitting, postures, auxiliary surfaces, electronic facilities and be easily reconfigurable	0.6	0.1	5.3	1964	28.7872473	This is enabled by fully autonomous driving feature - for Tesla that is EUR10,000.
FC219	Trust in technology in the case of bad weather	Dissemination and promotional campaigns about safety mechanisms in the case of bad weather.	0.3	0.0	7.5	751	46.2326542	Digital Marketing Campaign costs Facebook & LinkedIn: Cost per click (CPC): 0.51\$ and 5.61\$ respectively. Assumed budget for 2000 clicks on FCB and 500 clicks on LinkedIn.. Distributed on 5 years.

Table 6: UCII 3Es Indicators - Continuation

LEVEL 3 FAIRNESS CHARACTERISTICS		FAIRNESS MEASURES	3Es KPI				COST DESCRIPTION (All costs are distributed on a 5 year life of a car with interest rate 5%)	
			EFFECTIVENESS INDICATOR		EQUITY INDICATOR	COST (€/YEAR)		EFFICIENCY INDICATOR
			Women (A)	Men (B)	A/B	G		A/G
FC637	Vehicle behaviour under sportive driving	Education about sportive driving mode when it is activated: Benefits and disadvantages	0.7	0.1	9.6	750	96.2695111	Infotainment + sport driving feature.
FC6319	Importance of optimising well-being of other road users to determine vehicle behaviour	Education on the social benefits of the various driving parameters for users to make informed decisions when selecting the automatic driving parameter	0.0	0.0	#DIV/0!	1080	0	Assumed one month promotional campaign the cost like below.
FC531	Perception of public health when driving without steering wheel	Promotion campaigns for public awareness about benefits of automated driving versus manual/conventional cars	0.2	0.0	5.6	2160	8.66573611	It is not related to vehicle, so it cannot be distributed on multiple periods, it is a point input investment Social Media Campaign EUR4,000 – EUR7,000 per month.

Use Case III: Bike sharing services

Table 7: UCIII 3Es Indicators for the profile “Women as a homogeneous group”

LEVEL 3 FAIRNESS CHARACTERISTICS	FAIRNESS MEASURES	3Es KPI					COST DESCRIPTION	
		EFFECTIVENESS INDICATOR		EQUITY INDICATOR	COST (€/YEAR)	EFFICIENCY INDICATOR		
		Women (A)	Men (B)	A/B	G	A/G		
FC333	Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo.	Provide accessories to facilitate travelling with children or shopping (child seat or basket)	0.0	0.0	0.0	437	0.0	Option 1: Mounting on existing bikes, child seat and basket (if possible): 195EUR; Option 2: Electric bike with child seat and basket: 680-1700EUR, average: EUR/1190 EUR, economic life: 3 years.
FC312	Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling	Separate cycle lanes free from vehicular traffic	0.4	0.3	1.3	14276	2.8	"The City of Portland estimates that a raised concrete 2-way cycle track costs EUR698 per foot (EUR282 for construction, EUR71 for project management, EUR28 for engineering, EUR168 for overhead, and EUR149 for contingency)"
FC237	Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes	Provide recommendations to customers with alternative routes avoiding high-speed roads from point A to B.	0.2	0.1	2.1	1885	13.2	Traffic info board (led+solar) 1sqm costs around 272 EUR. On a network of 130 km (Madrid) if we need to install 30 info boards that is: 8160 EUR (3 years, 5%), but they have to be fed with some info, and that (real time traffic management system) costs much more.
FC132	Available to those in low-income neighbourhoods	Implement plans to establish stations in low-income communities trying to make them available within 400m radius in these communities.	0.1	0.5	0.2	26150	0.4	Digital Marketing Campaign: FCB & LinkedIn: CPC: 0.51\$ and 5.61\$ respectively. Assumed budget for 2000 clicks on FCB and 500 clicks on LinkedIn.
FC322	Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling	More inclusive promotional campaigns including disability persons.	0.0	0.0	0.0	3252	0.0	23 EUR/bike is installation of safety light, economic life: 1 year. Total price depends on the bike fleet.
FC114	Safety equipment provided including helmets, hi-vis vest, rain ponchos	Ensure that all bikes have well-functioning safety lights and brakes	0.1	0.4	0.2	123	77.4	58 new bikes cost \$70,120, or an average of \$1,208.97 per bike. In EUR: 1028 per bike; Economic life 3 years.

Table 7: UCIII 3Es Indicators - Continuation

LEVEL 3 FAIRNESS CHARACTERISTICS	FAIRNESS MEASURES	3Es KPI					COST DESCRIPTION	
		EFFECTIVENESS INDICATOR		EQUITY INDICATOR	COST (€/YEAR)	EFFICIENCY INDICATOR		
		Women (A)	Men (B)	A/B	G	A/G		
FC412	Avoid hilly terrain in the development of cycle networks where possible.	Offer electric bikes to customers	0.2	0.4	0.4	378	43.7	Madrid has 130 km of cycle lanes (inner city). HFS costs around 20 EUR/sqm. If we assume that we need to cover 10 km with HFC that is 100 sqm and around 2000 EUR. It can last for 10 years.
FC421	All weather cycle-friendly infrastructure	The cycling lanes should be prepared for rainy days in terms of friction, etc.	0.0	0.0	0.0	260	0.0	Cost of changing room building is 1720-1920 EUR per sqm, it is assumed 2 buildings (on each end of bike lane) of 50 sqm Economic life of 20 years.
FC144	Attractive changing facilities	Genderised changing rooms with required commodities for women.	0.0	0.0	0.0	14596.4	0.0	Media campaign - one month.
FC332	Safe cycle routes for cycling with children	Lobby local authority for safe routes to school etc. and publicly monitoring progress.	0.1	0.2	0.6	3400	3.4	One 19-dock station and six 15-dock stations cost \$280,931. (That puts each of the smaller docking station at \$38,660 each and the larger station at nearly \$49,000). One smaller dock station is considered => 32860 EUR. Economic life 10 years

Use Case IV: Employability in the transport sector

Table 8: UCIV 3Es Indicators for the profile “Women as a homogeneous group”

FC Code	LEVEL 3 FAIRNESS CHARACTERISTICS	FAIRNESS MEASURES	3Es KPI					COST DESCRIPTION
			EFFECTIVENESS INDICATOR		EQUITY INDICATOR	COST (€/YEAR)	EFFICIENCY INDICATOR	
			Women (A)	Men (B)	A/B	G	A/G	
FC313	Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time; (Opportunity for flexible working)	Ability of staff to change shift patterns at short notice to reflect caring needs	0.1	0.1	1.0	24336	0.4	An average irregular engagement (call for work in less than 24h from duty) of a train driver (train crew/dispatcher) is 3 times per month -> this costs a Railway Operator 30 EURcent/km*2*50 km (trip costs) +120 EUR + 10h*18.5 EUR/h (10 hours is duty + travelling from home and to home) = 338 EUR * 3 times per month * 12 months = 12168 EUR of excess cost of employer per a train driver. If we assume 5 times (maximum) of irregular engagement that is: 20280 EUR/year per train driver; In case if the Department for train traffic employees 20 train drivers and each has 3 times per month (36 times per year) an irregular engagement that is 10*12168 = 121680 EUR per year; Now, if we assume a 20% of increase in irregular engagement of train crew due to some additional reasons (such as those related to caring needs) that would be 121680*0.2 = 24336 EUR more per year.
FC123	Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed (Recruitment - Written and formal Recruitment polices (that cannot be altered by frontline managers))	Use a wide range of media platforms for adverts to ensure wider spread	0.0	0.5	0.0	1050	0.0	Price 840 EUR is per month for 5 jobs. Price per individual job is 210 EUR per month. Assumed: One job posting for 5 jobs and one for individual job per year: 840+210 = 1050 (Platform: Monster)
FC255	Security staff available to intervene in case of need. (Additional safety process are in place for lone working/night time working)	Ensure security and police support can be accessed rapidly by staff.	0.0	0.4	0.0	20900	0.0	Salary of security guard per year

Table 8: UCIV 3Es Indicators - Continuation

FC Code	LEVEL 3 FAIRNESS CHARACTERISTICS	FAIRNESS MEASURES	3Es KPI					COST DESCRIPTION
			EFFECTIVENESS INDICATOR		EQUITY INDICATOR	COST (€/YEAR)	EFFICIENCY INDICATOR	
			Women (A)	Men (B)	A/B	G	A/G	
FC451	Diversity training in general and specifically for ethnicity	To have ready a written CSR protocol / policy	0.3	0.2	2.2	1110000	0.0	Assumption: 2% of profit should be allocated to CSR activities per year in next 3 years. DB profit in 2018 was 680 m EUR => allocation to CSR should be 13.6 m EUR.
FC252	Applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment;	Organize training sessions for all the staff	0.0	0	0.0	1800	0.0	Total number of attendees: 100; 4 groups per 25; 2 rounds. In total: 4*2 = 8 sessions, each session 60 minutes; Price of trainee per session: 200 EUR In total 1600 EUR + training material (200 EUR) = 1800 EUR OR 225 EUR per session
FC214	Integrate the company's commitment to gender equality into all of its communication activities and HR policies;	Gender neutral employment advertisement	0.0	0	0.0	1050	0.0	Price 840 EUR is per month for 5 jobs. Price per individual job is 210 EUR per month. Assumed: One job posting for 5 jobs and one for individual job per year: 840+210 = 1050 (Platform: Monster)
FC115	Ensuring gender pay equality for equivalent positions;	Flexibility against maternity to avoid glass ceilings in the professional development process of women.	0.4	0	0.0	1400	25.4	The formula is: Training cost per employee (women coming back from maternity) = total training expenses per year/number of attendants (women) per year. If we assume that we spent 2000 EUR on training material, 3000 EUR on lost productivity and 2000 on new laptops during the year that is in total 7000 EUR on training for the year. In an organization of 1000 employees (small railway enterprise) with 50% of women, if we have a 1% of those coming back from maternity leave, that is 5 women employees per year. 7000/5=1400 EUR
FC215	Ensure that the male-female ratio of internal promotions in different job categories is in line with the average male-female ratio of the company staff;	Equity plans going beyond legal statements	0.0	0	0.0	5325	0.0	Belongs to FC11; Conduct an equality audit (promotional activity - 1300 EUR) + implementation and monitoring of equality policy (13th salary of a HR manager): 1300 + 4025 = 5325

Table 8: UCIV 3Es Indicators - Continuation

FC Code	LEVEL 3 FAIRNESS CHARACTERISTICS	FAIRNESS MEASURES	3Es KPI					COST DESCRIPTION
			EFFECTIVENESS INDICATOR		EQUITY INDICATOR	COST (€/YEAR)	EFFICIENCY INDICATOR	
			Women (A)	Men (B)	A/B	G	A/G	
FC133	Family friendly working conditions for different categories of workers (e.g. professions that require prolonged absence from home)	Allow flexible part-time working arrangements like reduced working hours or home office provisions	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	Home office provision does not generate cost for employer only for an employee (extra heating and electricity cost). Maybe just the fact that some employees may not work efficiently without supervision. Also, for employee benefit in decreased external childcare hours and costs. On the other side reducing workers' hours may create a lost "opportunity cost" of lost sales. However, this cannot hold for transport service industry. By the cost <0 I mean that this measure provides more benefits for both, employee and employer
FC132	Equal employment policies: Policies are used within the organisation to support fair recruitment and promotion processes for women, and meet national legal requirements (including Equal Employment policies);	All roles/vacancies are open and available for both men and women	0.1	0	0.0	6375	1.5	Equal Opportunities policies incur development costs and continuing costs of training and dissemination. Plus, increased job advertising costs and time to conduct selection fairly; collection and analysis of data to monitor Equal Opportunities; Development costs: 50% increase of monthly salary for 2 HR workers (overtime work on EEO policy implementation, fair selection, monitoring): average monthly salary of HR manager: 4025 -> 2*2012.5=4025 + continuing costs of training (1300 EUR) + advertisement (1050): 6375

4.1.1 Effectiveness of recommendations for the Top 10 FCs for Women

Effectiveness measures the extent to which input generates its objectives (Athanasopoulos, 1998); it is related to the question of which fairness measure contribute most to the overall project objective of the Use Case. In other words, effectiveness describes the impact of the inputs in achieving the defined goals for each Use Case. The study assesses whether an innovation is likely to achieve the stated objectives and how well the objectives are met (i.e. to what extent will the implementation of an innovation increase the satisfaction of women and men and their fair participation in the transport sector). The effectiveness of the proposed intervention for the associated FC is measured by the extent to which the FC achieves the specific objective each Use Case and the general objective of DIAMOND.

Tables 5 to 8 lists the FCs along with their effectiveness scores, which are linked to the factors affecting women highlighted across the analysis (DIAMOND Project, 2021a).

Considering the nature of the Bayesian network (BN) approach, contribution of specific fairness measure to the overall goal takes into account its contribution to other fairness measures which are also necessary for achieving the overall goal of increasing the % of women using the railway services.

By running the BN simulations for each particular fairness measure and summing up the individual contributions of that measure to each of the other FMs which are also relevant for achieving the final goal (increased % of satisfaction of women as users of railway passenger services) we are obtaining the measures of effectiveness (column 3 and column 4 in table below) for woman as well as for men.

For instance, the KPI of effectiveness for women and men are 1.5 and 0.4 respectively for the FCI 14 “Level of service at the public transport access point”. While both women and men are dissatisfied with the level of service (LOS) of the public transport access point, women show high level of dissatisfaction and are disproportionately affected with the LOS compared to men. The higher indicator value for women means the implementation of the corresponding FM will benefit women more than men. Hence FCI 14 will be effective in minimising the accessibility disparities across the two groups. Since the current “**Level of service at the public transport access point**” limit the transport options and accessibility for women more than men. To understand the costs and consequences associated with each proposed fairness measure (FM), the efficiency and equity of each proposed fairness measure are similarly assessed (see section 2.1. for more information on how equity and efficiency have been calculated).

The following figures (Figure 3 - 6) illustrate the rank of fairness measures for all use-cases by effectiveness indicator. Fairness measure (which corresponds to fairness characteristic FCI 15 => Display the next services in the station) represents the most appreciated improvement from the aspect of women, as well in total (by satisfaction of men and women together). Measures related to seating design (FC323) and the supporting staff at the stations trained on equality and gender (FC318) are the least appreciated from the aspect of women. Due to the lack of space on the graphs complete name of the fairness measure is available in UC-related tables (Table 5 – UCI, Table 6 – UCII, Table 7 – UCIII, Table 8 – UCIV).

Figure 6. UCI – Sorting fairness measures by Effectiveness indicator

The most important fairness measure in UCII is related to education about sportive driving (corresponds to FC637), but the measures related to the main features of autonomous driving such as performing non-driving related tasks (FC224), automated speed control system (FC6327) and freedom in choosing the degree of interaction within the car cabin (FC229) are also highly appreciated measures.

Figure 7. UCII – Sorting fairness measures by effectiveness

In Use case III the most acceptable FMs are related to FC312 – Separate cycle lanes free from vehicular traffic, as well as the possibility for renting electric bikes (FC412) or the installation of variable message signs for cyclists (and other vulnerable road users) (FC237).

Figure 8. UCIII – Sorting fairness measures by effectiveness

In the overall objective of the UCIV, the measures related to flexible working especially with respect to maternity and its impact on career (FM that corresponds to FC115) as well as the efficient CSR policy management (FC451) has the highest share from the aspect of women satisfaction. On the other side measures related to security and policy supports as well as advertisement are appreciated only from the aspect of men.

Figure 9. UCIV – Sorting fairness measures by effectiveness

4.1.2 Efficiency of recommendations for the Top10FCs for Women

Efficiency or production efficiency (PE), is related to cost-effectiveness and measured by the ratio of produced outputs (i.e., service delivery) to the required inputs (such as labour, infrastructure, vehicle design, and capital investment) (Chen et al., 2019). The study seeks to provide information on the possible resources required to implement each proposed fairness measure and which

fairness measure is cost-effective in achieving the objectives of each Use Case (Athanasopoulos, 1998).

The Efficiency Indicator of each FM is the ratio of the Effectiveness indicator to the cost of implementing the FM. The Efficiency Indicator value can be translated into higher cost-effectiveness in achieving the project objective of equity. The efficiency is assessed by comparing the monetary cost of implementing intervention and the benefit (in terms of the effectiveness of achieving the specific objective) as a ratio. Tables 5, 6, 7 and 8 show the monetised cost for implementing each intervention (fairness measure) associated with each FC.

Since it is assumed that all fairness measures represent point-input continuous-output investments, the cost is calculated by applying a capital recovery factor ($A/P, i\%, n$) where P is a present value of an investment in fairness measure and A is an annuity equivalent to P, for a constant interest rate $i=5\%$ and respective economic life of an investment n.

Figures 7 – 10 summarize the effects of the most important FMs from the aspect of efficiency.

In the case of UCI, the highest efficiency is assigned to the fairness measure that enables an enhanced provision of train service related information in stations (FC115). Since this measure requires investments on a specific railway line or a network as a whole, it includes significant investments also. The indicator for FC115 in Figure 10 is reduced ~10 times in order to get it aligned with the rest of the indicators. The least efficient are the measures related to seating design (FC323) and to training the supporting staff in stations (FC318). Due to the lack of space on the graphs complete name of the fairness measure is available in UC-related tables (Table 5 – UCI, Table 6 – UCII, Table 7 – UCIII, Table 8 – UCIV).

Figure 10. UCI – Sorting fairness measures by efficiency

Efficiency related ranking in case of Use case II corresponds to the effectiveness ranking. The least efficient measures are related to education on the social benefits of the driving parameters (FC6319), ecological impact available for passengers in car cabin as well as relax atmosphere (FC521) within the cabin of AV (FC229).

Figure 11. UCII – Sorting fairness measures by efficiency

In Use case III the most efficient FM is related to the provision of well-equipped bikes in terms of safety lights and brakes (FC114), electric bike offer (FC412) as well as information boards for cyclists (FC237).

Figure 12. UCIII – Sorting fairness measures by efficiency

The most efficient FM in Use case IV is the measure related to flexibility against maternity in order to avoid glass ceilings in the professional development process of women (FC115).

Figure 13. UCIV – Sorting fairness measures by efficiency

4.1.3 Equity of recommendations for the Top10FCs for Women

In general terms, equity is related to how resources are distributed throughout society according to the needs of people (Athanasopoulos, 1998; Murray and Davis, 2001). The Equity Indicators indicates which of the proposed FMs promote fairness in the delivery of the transport service to all groups of women and the extent to which they contribute to the achievement of the Use Case goal and the overall project objective. The rationale is to advocate for investments and allocation of resources to implement the proposed interventions/FMs with the potential of benefiting the disadvantaged and closing the gender disparities in the delivery of transport services. The Equity indicator provides information for maximizing the fairness of distribution and minimizing disparities across groups such as disparities between racial, ethnic, age, and socioeconomic groups.

The 3Es KPIs for the FCs/FMs identified for four use-cases are measured through OBSERVATIONS and User satisfaction surveys are presented in the sections below.

In this specific case, the equity indicators represent the ratio of effectiveness of a specific fairness measure for women and the effectiveness of that fairness measure for man. Equity ratio higher than one indicates that a fairness measure contributes to satisfaction of women more than to satisfaction of men. In contrary, the equity ratio lower than one leads to unsatisfactory results. Therefore, those fairness measures are more preferable that generate higher equity ratio. However, since the aim is to achieve equity, we are preferring the ratio which is closer to 1, in order to improve the satisfaction of women without sacrificing too much the satisfaction of men.

For instance, Effectiveness indicators for FC114 and FC115, indicates that both FCs has the potential to minimise the disparities for women. In terms of equity, the ratio of the indicators for women and men suggests that both FCs will close the gender accessibility gap for women. However, FC114 will be 3.4 times more effective in promoting women satisfaction and use of public transport services than men, compared to 1.5 times for FC115. Even though the implementation of the proposed interventions for the FCs will promote the fairness of the transport system, investment in the FM for FC114 will be more effective in creating a fair system than FC115 with respect to equity.

Figures 11-14 summarise 3Es computational results for all UCs in terms of equity which will be achieved by proposed measures. Due to the lack of space on the graphs complete name of the

fairness measure is available in UC-related tables (Table 5 – UCI, Table 6 – UCII, Table 7 – UCIII, Table 8 – UCIV).

For UCI, the ranking of FMs significantly differs from that of effectiveness and efficiency. In terms of equity, the most important are those measures related to appropriate station access (ramps, escalators and lifts for persons with disabilities) which corresponds to FC114, coordination of timetables between the different transport modes in stations (FC112) and the availability of information that indicates and allows access to key destination (FC111). In terms of least preferred measures from the equity aspect, the situation is the same as in the case of efficiency and effectiveness indicators.

Figure 14. UCI – Sorting fairness measures by equity

The most important fairness measures in use-case II which will highly contribute to equity are education about sportive driving mode (FC637) and automated systems for speed controlling (FC6327). Measures related to the degree of interaction in the cabin of AV or vehicle design are less important from the equity aspect.

Figure 15. UCII – Sorting fairness measures by equity

For UCIII, the FMs that achieve the highest equity are related to information boards for cyclists (FC237), separate cycle lanes (FC312) and provision of safe cycle routes for family cycling (FC332).

Figure 16. UCIII – Sorting fairness measures by equity

In the case of UCIV, two of the most important FMs from the aspect of equity are the measure that relates to CSR protocol readiness (FC451) as well as the ability of changing the shift patterns on short notice which is an almost impossible measure for implementation in some timetable dependent work engagements (train driver, conductor etc...).

Figure 17. UCIV – Sorting fairness measures by equity

5. Sensitivity and sustainability analysis

5.1 Introduction

This Sensitivity Analysis (SA) is performed to assess how the hierarchy of level 3 FCs changes according to **gender** and to assess the **sustainability** of the results of the DIAMOND's project. This SA is carried out as a means of validating and calibrating the numerical data for each Use Case. This is useful in reducing uncertainty in multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) and providing information about the robustness of the outputs of the fairness measures proposed in the project. The SA illustrates the impact of small changes to specific input parameters (weights and hierarchy of Fairness Characteristics Level 1) on the outcomes of decisions (hierarchy of level 3 Fairness Characteristics). The section assesses the sensitivity analysis per gender and, the sustainability of the results with respect to time and space/culture (geographical location).

- ◆ Sensitivity analysis per gender: Assesses the difference in response between women and men on the top 10 FCs Level 3.
- ◆ Sustainability over time: Assesses how the final results (weights and hierarchy of Fairness Characteristics Level 3) will be affected by modifications in the preferences on main topics (Fairness Characteristics level 1) with the time.
- ◆ Sustainability over Space: Assesses how the results are affected or can be affected by different cultures, for instance, Eastern European (Poland) and Western European (Spain) cultures.

SA is a crucial step of any decision analysis and result communication process. SA is often used to quantify the importance of each parameter in the decision modelling application and provides essential insights on the behaviour of the system, as well as on its response to changes in the model inputs (Borgonovo and Plischke, 2016). According to spiceLogic Inc (2020), decision making cannot be said to be robust, without a proper sensitivity analysis. The solution to a decision problem, and the global ranking of alternatives, may not provide enough information to the Decision Maker (DM) to make a final decision. Therefore, by providing a quantitative and rigorous overview of how changes in the weights and hierarchy of Level 1 Fairness Characteristics will influence the output of level 3 Fairness Characteristics and then on the associated fairness measures, this SA will offer the DM an additional layer of information for more informed decision-making.

Critical FCs in achieving the goals of the Use Cases are presented for the attention of the decision-makers. The report conducts a policy assessment of the various FCs identified in the DIAMOND project to demonstrate the robustness and the policy implication of the proposed measures to verify their impact on the overall goal of the DIAMOND project.

5.2 Sensitivity analysis per gender

Use Case I

- Differences between TOP10 FCs for WOMEN and for MEN

TOP10 level 3 FCs were calculated independently for WOMEN and for MEN applying the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) to obtain level 1 and level 2 FCs local weights combined with the weights obtained using Bayesian networks (BNs) to obtain level 3 FCs local weights (DIAMOND Project, 2021). The tables below show the top 10 FCs for women and men users of Public Transport - Railways

The TOP10 fairness characteristics for WOMEN can be seen in Table 9.

Table 9: UCI Top 10 FCs for Women

FC code	FC description	Norm. weight AHP x BN
FC321	Offering adequate personal space;	0.03615
FC323	Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating).	0.03022
FC322	Improved ventilation and air-conditioning;	0.02843
FC111	Walking time from the points of interest to the public transport access points	0.02803
FC116	Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc.	0.02606
FC316	Complaint information point in case of violations to personal safety;	0.02541
FC315	Visibility of the surrounding area of the station;	0.02525
FC115	Number of service available within the transport infrastructure	0.02507
FC112	Reliability of the service modes available	0.02409
FC117	Integration with alternative shared mobility service for last mile connections, including bike, scooter and car sharing	0.02409

The TOP10 fairness characteristics for MEN can be seen in Table 10.

Table 10: UCI Top 10 FCs for Men

FCs Code	FC Level 3 description	Norm. weight AHP x BN
FC317	Availability of hospitality rooms where to ask for help in case of aggression or need;	0.02558
FC311	Number and typology of incidents	0.02517
FC318	Display advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicizing helpline numbers.	0.02383

FCs Code	FC Level 3 description	Norm. weight AHP x BN
FC312	Presence and visibility of CCTV system;	0.02252
FC217	Safe and step free pedestrian crossings and sidewalks surrounding the stations;	0.02170
FC323	Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating).	0.02161
FC118	Availability of on-demand transport services including taxi and paratransit	0.02143
FC117	Integration with alternative shared mobility service for last mile connections, including bike, scooter and car sharing	0.02142
FC219	Fare gates to accommodate a wide variety of users;	0.02132
FC214	Tactile surfaces to provide wayfinding information to people with reduced visual capabilities;	0.02129

The comparison of the top 10 FCs for men and women indicates that both men and women have different needs in the use of public transport; 80% of the top 10 FCs were found to be gender specific. Men and women only shared two of the FCs in the top10 FCs.

- ◆ FC117 Integration with alternative shared mobility service for last mile connections, including bike, scooter and car sharing.
- ◆ FC323 Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating).
- Differences between the satisfaction showed by WOMEN and by MEN regarding the TOPI0 FCs for WOMEN

Applying an ANOVA analysis to the TOPI0 factors obtained for WOMEN as a homogeneous group, and after verifying that we had a sufficient number of respondents to get a significant result, given the number of ranges for a specific socio-demographic characteristic, we concluded the next:

For UC-I, men and women were found to significantly differ in opinion for the following list of FCs:

- ◆ FC321: Offering adequate personal space
- ◆ FC323: Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction...
- ◆ FC116: Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train....
- ◆ FC316: Complaint information point in case of violations to personal safety
- ◆ FC315: Visibility of the surrounding area of the station
- ◆ FC115: Number of service available within the transport infrastructure
- ◆ FC112: Reliability of the service modes available

Use Case II

- Differences between TOP10 FCs for WOMEN and for MEN

As in use case I, TOP10 Fairness Characteristics were calculated for MEN and for WOMEN, using only responses coming from men or from women respectively in the AHP and BNs analysis.

The TOP10 level 3 fairness characteristics for women can be seen in Table 11.

Table 11: UCII Top 10 FCs for Women

FCs code	Description FC	Norm. weight AHP x BN
FC228	Perception of boredom	0.02270
FC229	Perception of joy	0.02270
FC219	Bad weather	0.02050
FC6327	Importance on controlling speed	0.01987
FC213	Perception of dislike delegating decisions	0.01936
FC521	Perception of reduction of ecological impact	0.01881
FC223	Perception of the degree of interaction between passengers	0.01835
FC633	Overall preference of sportive driving	0.01827
FC6319	Importance of optimising well-being of other road users to determine vehicle behaviour	0.01827
FC224	Driving when performing simultaneous tasks in comfortable external environment	0.01822

The TOP10 fairness characteristics for men can be seen in Table 12.

Table 12: UCII Top 10 FCs for Men

Code	FC Level 3	Norm. weight AHP x BN
FC211	Perception of trust industry minimizing risks for humans	0.02855
FC213	Perception of dislike delegating decisions	0.02786
FC219	Bad weather	0.02635
FC2112	Event affecting personal safety	0.02575
FC521	Perception of reduction of ecological impact	0.02290
FC212	Perception of doubts in technologies	0.02140
FC6412	Importance of clearness of the information provided	0.01979
FC222	Perception of the degree of simultaneity	0.01792
FC214	Perception of overall trust	0.01769
FC6319	Importance of optimising well-being of other road users to determine vehicle behaviour	0.01699

Comparing the top 10 FCs ranking according gender, both men and women were found to differ 40% of the top 10 FCs. There are four FCs within the top10 for both men and women:

- ◆ FC219 Bad weather.
- ◆ FC213 Perception of dislike delegating decisions.
- ◆ FC521 Perception of reduction of ecological impact.
- ◆ FC6319 Importance of optimising well-being of other road users to determine vehicle behaviour.

These four FCs are main issues affecting the acceptance of autonomous vehicles for both men and women. The other 60% of the top10 FCs are specific for each gender.

- Differences between satisfaction showed by WOMEN and by MEN regarding the TOPI0 FCs for WOMEN

For UC-II, the ANOVA analysis of the responses did not show any significant difference in responses between women and men for the top 10 FCs.

This means that this analysis is not able to explain the “acceptance paradox” for the autonomous vehicle saying that women, who initially could need more the autonomous driving to optimize their errand travels, have a lower level of acceptance than men to the autonomous vehicles, as it is shown in (Havlíčková *et al.*, 2019).

Use Case III

- Differences between TOPI0 FCs for WOMEN and for MEN

The TOPI0 Fairness Characteristics calculated for MEN and for WOMEN, using only responses coming from men or from women respectively in the AHP and BNs analysis are shown in Tables 13 and 14. The TOPI0 level 3 fairness characteristics for women and men in order to increase their use of the bicycle sharing system are shown in Tables 13 and 14 respectively.

Table 13: UCIII Top 10 FCs for Women

FC code	FC description	Norm. weight AHP x BN
FC322	Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling	0.06690
FC422	Cycling rain Poncho	0.05661
FC412	Avoid hilly terrain in the development of cycle networks where possible.	0.05239
FC421	All weather cycle-friendly infrastructure	0.04650
FC144	Attractive changing facilities	0.04446
FC333	Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo.	0.04342
FC332	Safe cycle routes for cycling with children	0.03542
FC321	Availability of end-of-trip cycling facilities	0.03502
FC312	Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling	0.03120
FC237	Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes	0.03054

Table 14: UCIII Top 10 FCs for Men

FC Code	FC Level 3 description	Norm. weight AHP x BN
FC412	Avoid hilly terrain in the development of cycle networks where possible.	0.05910
FC411	Electric bikes in bike-share fleet	0.05654
FC421	All weather cycle-friendly infrastructure	0.04716
FC422	Cycling rain Poncho	0.04069
FC333	Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo.	0.03908
FC331	Education on practical cycling (cycling with children and cargo)	0.03589
FC321	Availability of end-of-trip cycling facilities	0.03549
FC311	Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling to demystify the myth about cycling in low-income and minority neighbourhoods	0.03430
FC332	Safe cycle routes for cycling with children	0.03407
FC215	Safety of the environment around the cyclist to prevent accident	0.02776

The comparison of the top 10 rankings for men and women shows that 60% of the top 10 FCs were common for men and women. Both genders agreed that these six FCs are the main issues affecting the use of bicycle-sharing services and are likely to increase the usage of bicycle sharing services if addressed:

- ◆ FC422 Cycling rain poncho
- ◆ FC412 Avoid hilly terrain in the development of cycle networks where possible
- ◆ FC421 All-weather cycle-friendly infrastructure
- ◆ FC333 Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo.
- ◆ FC332 Safe cycle routes for cycling with children
- ◆ FC321 Availability of end-of-trip cycling facilities

The other 40% of the top 10 FCs are preferences or priorities specific for each gender.

- Differences between satisfaction showed by WOMEN and by MEN regarding the TOP10 FCs for WOMEN

For UC-III, the ANOVA analysis of the responses shows that women and men differ significantly in preferences on the FC below:

- ◆ FC312: Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling

Use Case IV

- Differences between TOPI0 FCs for WOMEN and for MEN

TOPI0 Fairness Characteristics were calculated for MEN and for WOMEN, using only responses coming from men or from women respectively in the AHP and BNs analysis.

The TOPI0 level 3 fairness characteristics for Women and Men regarding a fairer transport employment system shown in Tables 15 and 16:

Table 15: UCIV Top 10 FCs for Women

FC code	FC description	Norm. weight AHP x BN
FC123	Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed;	0.07701
FC451	Diversity training (re ethnicity);	0.07546
FC313	Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time;	0.06431
FC255	Security staff available to intervene in case of need.	0.04744
FC252	Applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment;	0.04647
FC214	Integrate the company's commitment to gender equality into all of its communication activities and HR policies;	0.04625
FC215	Ensure that the male-female ratio of internal promotions in different job categories is in line with the average male-female ratio of the company staff;	0.04129
FC115	Ensuring gender pay equality for equivalent positions;	0.04033
FC133	Family friendly policies – maternity and paternity leave;	0.03877
FC132	Equal employment policies: Policies are used within the organisation to support fair recruitment and promotion processes for women, and meet national legal requirements (including Equal Employment policies);	0.03660

Table 16: UCIV Top 10 FCs for Men

FC Code	FC Level 3 description	Norm. Weight AHP x BN
FC123	Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed;	0.05698
FC125	Ensure employment decisions are based on objective issues related to the job;	0.05257
FC311	Supported career/carer breaks;	0.04614
FC255	Security staff available to intervene in case of need.	0.04548
FC313	Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time;	0.04532

FC Code	FC Level 3 description	Norm. Weight AHP x BN
FC112	On the job training for men and women to negate cultural stereotypes associated with women and specific roles and tasks in the transport sector;	0.04351
FC133	Family friendly policies – maternity and paternity leave;	0.04288
FC321	Have access to funds to travel to work;	0.03946
FC115	Ensuring gender pay equality for equivalent positions;	0.03651
FC111	All jobs are available and suitable for both men and women (and there is a more equal balance between genders across all occupations, levels and jobs in transport)	0.03611

Comparing both rankings, five FCs within the top10 FCs (50%) were found common to both men and women. These are considered as issues that if improved would make employment in the transport sector fairer and increase percentage of women working in the sector. These FCs are:

- ◆ FC123 Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed.
- ◆ FC313 Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time.
- ◆ FC255 Security staff available to intervene in case of need.
- ◆ FC115 Ensuring gender pay equality for equivalent positions.
- ◆ FC133 Family friendly policies – maternity and paternity leave.

The remaining five or 50% of the top10 FCs were found to be gender specific.

- Differences between satisfaction showed by WOMEN and by MEN regarding the TOP10 FCs for WOMEN

For UC-IV, the ANOVA analysis showed Not Significant difference in responses between women and men for the top 10 FCs.

5.3 Sustainability of results over time for the profile “Women as a homogeneous group”

This section assesses the robustness of the hierarchized list of the FCs over time (in the present and in the future) the following use-cases (1: public transport, railway; 2: autonomous vehicles and 4: transport employment). Several sensitivity analyses were performed on the input parameters by varying the weightings of each Level I fairness characteristics. To determine how changes in women priorities with regard to the fairness characteristics over time will affect the outcomes for users of public transport infrastructure and services, the weights of each level I fairness characteristic is increased by 50% to provide insights into the robustness of the analysis against future changes in women priorities of the Level I fairness characteristics.

Table 17 shows the description of what it considered present and future scenario in each use case. Use case 3 is not included since it was only analysed the present scenario, no future scenario was foreseen (see DIAMOND deliverable D2.1).

Table 17: DIAMOND Present and Future Scenarios

Use case	ID vertex	Scenario
1. Public transport. Railway	V1	Railway stations of today
	V4	Stations of the future. Hyperloop
2. Autonomous vehicles	V2	Automated vehicles of today (below level 4 of automation)
	V5	Fully autonomous vehicles (L4+)
4. Transport employment	V3	Transport employment today
	V6	Employment of the future. Incorporation of technological advances in the transport sector such as drone logistics.

Use Case I

Table 18 shows the top10 FCs obtained for UCI in the PRESENT scenario for WOMEN as a homogeneous group.

Table 18: Initial Hierarchized list of UCI FCs (Vertex I)

FC Code	Level 1 FC	Level 2 FC	Level 3 FC	Norm. Weight	Rank
FC321	Safety and security	Overcrowding and emergency situations	Offering adequate personal space;	0.03615	1
FC323	Safety and security	Overcrowding and emergency situations	Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating).	0.03022	2
FC322	Safety and security	Overcrowding and emergency situations	Improved ventilation and air-conditioning;	0.02843	3
FC111	Accessibility of the service	Service availability and efficiency	Walking time from the points of interest to the public transport access points	0.02803	4
FC116	Accessibility of the service	Service availability and efficiency	Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc.	0.02606	5
FC316	Safety and security	Harassment and pickpocketing	Complaint information point in case of violations to personal safety;	0.02541	6
FC315	Safety and security	Harassment and pickpocketing	Visibility of the surrounding area of the station;	0.02525	7
FC115	Accessibility of the service	Service availability and efficiency	Number of service available within the transport infrastructure	0.02507	8
FC112	Accessibility of the service	Service availability and efficiency	Reliability of the service modes available	0.02409	9
FC117	Accessibility of the service	Service availability and efficiency	Integration with alternative shared mobility service for last mile connections, including bike, scooter and car sharing	0.02409	9

Table 19 shows the sensitivity analysis over time for use-case I vertex I of the PRESENT scenario.

The results in the table show the initial hierarchized top 10 FCs for women as well as the top 10 FCs if the weights of level I FCs are increased by 50%. Please note that the FCs in bold are those maintained from the initial hierarchy. This shows for the UC I how robust are the results presented for PRESENT scenarios (and for the profile WOMEN as a homogeneous group) in the mid and long term.

Table 19: Sensitivity analysis over time for use case I vertex I (Today). Note: FCs in bold are those maintained from the initial hierarchy

Top10 for women		+50% Level I FC: Accessibility of the service		+50% Level I FC: Design of the infrastructure		+50% Level I FC: Safety and security	
<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>
FC321	0.03615	FC111	0.04326	FC2112	0.03020	FC321	0.05638
FC323	0.03022	FC116	0.04021	FC214	0.02931	FC323	0.04712
FC322	0.02843	FC115	0.03869	FC215	0.02931	FC322	0.04434
FC111	0.02606	FC112	0.03717	FC218	0.02889	FC316	0.03963
FC116	0.02606	FC117	0.03717	FC212	0.02869	FC315	0.03938
FC316	0.02541	FC118	0.03717	FC216	0.02806	FC311	0.03742
FC315	0.02525	FC113	0.03565	FC217	0.02806	FC317	0.03742
FC115	0.02507	FC114	0.03109	FC219	0.02806	FC318	0.03595
FC112	0.02409	FC321	0.02790	FC211	0.02764	FC314	0.03472
FC117	0.02409	FC323	0.02332	FC321	0.02543	FC312	0.03389

The sensitivity analysis developed shows that the final top10 hierarchy changes less if the users of the system evaluate a 50% higher the cluster of FCs related to the accessibility of the service. In this case a 70% of the preferences remain the same. The hierarchy is similar in a 50% also if the cluster of FCs related to safety and security increases in weight by a 50%. Finally, only one FC, FC321 offering adequate personal space, is maintained from the initial list if the cluster of fairness characteristics is evaluated a 50% higher. This indicates that this FC is very important even if huge changes in priorities (level I FCs) are produced. In addition, it should be noted that based on the work performed within DIAMOND, people are more concerned about safety and accessibility of the public transport system and not that much on its design, and thus a huge increase is not expected for level I FC design of the infrastructure.

From an overall perspective, 43% (on average) of the top 10 FCs remain the same. This result indicates the robustness of the results in the mid-term (it has been defined that when the sensitivity analysis shows between 20-80% of changes results are robust in the mid-term, if the percentage of changes is less than 20% it would be robust in the long term, and if more than 80% of FCs change then it would be robust in the short term since any small change in the context would change the preferences drastically).

Table 20 shows the top10 FCs obtained for UCI in the FUTURE scenario (HYPERLOOP stations) for WOMEN as a homogeneous group.

Table 20: Initial Hierarchized list of UCI FCs (Vertex 4)

FC Code	Level 1 FC	Level 2 FC	Level 3 FC	Norm. Weight	Rank
FC321	Safety and security	Overcrowding and emergency situations	Offering adequate personal space;	0.04441	1
FC323	Safety and security	Overcrowding and emergency situations	Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating).	0.03712	2
FC322	Safety and security	Overcrowding and emergency situations	Improved ventilation and air-conditioning;	0.03493	3
FC111	Accessibility of the service	Service availability and efficiency	Walking time from the points of interest to the public transport access points	0.03481	4
FC116	Accessibility of the service	Service availability and efficiency	Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc.	0.03237	5
FC316	Safety and security	Harassment and pickpocketing	Complaint information point in case of violations to personal safety;	0.03121	6
FC115	Accessibility of the service	Service availability and efficiency	Number of service available within the transport infrastructure	0.03114	7
FC315	Safety and security	Harassment and pickpocketing	Visibility of the surrounding area of the station;	0.03102	8
FC112	Accessibility of the service	Service availability and efficiency	Reliability of the service modes available	0.02992	9
FC117	Accessibility of the service	Service availability and efficiency	Integration with alternative shared mobility service for last mile connections, including bike, scooter and car sharing	0.02992	9

Table 21 shows the sensitivity analysis for the vertex of the future (V4).

The results in the table show the initial hierarchized list of the top 10 FCs for women as well as the top 10 FC when the weights of the level 1 FCs are increased by 50%. Please note that FCs in bold are those maintained from the initial hierarchy. This shows for the UC 1 how robust are the results presented for FUTURE scenarios (and for the profile WOMEN as a homogeneous group) in the mid and long term.

Table 21: Sensitivity analysis over time for use case 1 vertex 4 (Tomorrow). Note: FCs in bold are those maintained from the initial hierarchy.

Top10 for women		+50% Level 1 FC: Accessibility of the service		+50% Level 1 FC: Design of the infrastructure		+50% Level 1 FC: Safety and security	
FC	weight	FC	weight	FC	weight	FC	weight
FC321	0.04441	FC111	0.05280	FC321	0.03660	FC321	0.06990
FC323	0.03712	FC116	0.04909	FC323	0.03059	FC323	0.05842
FC322	0.03493	FC115	0.04723	FC322	0.02879	FC322	0.05498
FC111	0.03481	FC112	0.04537	FC111	0.02802	FC316	0.04913
FC116	0.03224	FC117	0.04537	FC116	0.02605	FC315	0.04882
FC316	0.03121	FC118	0.04537	FC316	0.02572	FC311	0.04639
FC115	0.03114	FC113	0.04535	FC315	0.02556	FC317	0.04639
FC315	0.03102	FC114	0.03795	FC115	0.02506	FC318	0.04457
FC112	0.02992	FC321	0.03442	FC311	0.02429	FC314	0.04305
FC117	0.02992	FC323	0.02877	FC317	0.02429	FC312	0.04238

The sensitivity analysis over time for the vertex of the future of use case I shows that if the weight of level I fairness characteristics increases by 50%, i.e. if the priorities changes giving more importance to the accessibility of the service, 70% of the top 10 FCs are maintained. 80% of the top 10 FCs are maintained if the level I FC design of the infrastructure is increased by 50%; and 50% of the initial FCs are maintained if the level I FC safety and security is increased by 50%.

On average 67% of the top 10FCs remain the same indicating that the results are robust in the mid-term.

Use Case II

Table 22 shows the top10 FCs obtained for UCII in the PRESENT scenario (automation level lower than L4) for women.

Table 22: Initial Hierarchized list of UCII FCs (Vertex 2)

FC Code	Level 1 FC	Level 2 FC	Level 3 FC	Norm. Weight	Rank
FC228	Comfort	Simultaneity	Perception of boredom	0.02270	1
FC229	Comfort	Simultaneity	Perception of joy	0.02270	1
FC219	Comfort	Trust in technology	Bad weather	0.02051	3
FC6327	Design option	Vehicle behaviour	Importance on controlling speed	0.01987	4
FC213	Comfort	Trust in technology	Perception of dislike delegating decisions	0.01936	5
FC521	Environment	Emissions	Perception of reduction of ecological impact	0.01881	6
FC223	Comfort	Simultaneity	Perception of the degree of interaction between passengers	0.01835	7
FC633	Design option	Vehicle behaviour	Overall preference of sportive driving	0.01828	8
FC6319	Design option	Vehicle behaviour	Importance of optimising well-being of other road users to determine vehicle behaviour	0.01828	8
FC224	Comfort	Simultaneity	Driving when performing simultaneous tasks in comfortable external environment	0.01822	10

Table 23 shows the sensitivity analysis for the vertex in the present scenario (V2). The results in the table show the initial hierarchized list of the top 10 FCs for women as well as the top 10 FC when the weights of the level I FCs are increased by 50%. Please note that FCs in bold are those maintained from the initial hierarchy. This shows for the UC II how robust are the results presented for PRESENT scenarios (and for the profile WOMEN as a homogeneous group) in the mid and long term.

Table 23: Sensitivity analysis over time for use case II vertex 2 (Today). Note: FCs in bold are those maintained from the initial hierarchy.

Top10 for women		+50% Level I FC: Safety and security		+50% Level I FC: Comfort		+50% Level I FC: Mobility		+50% Level I FC: Economy		+50% Level I FC: Environment		+50% Level I FC: Design option	
<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>
FC228	0.02270	FC228	0.02171	FC228	0.03268	FC343	0.02144	FC228	0.02230	FC521	0.03021	FC6327	0.02532
FC229	0.02270	FC229	0.02171	FC229	0.03268	FC228	0.02064	FC229	0.02230	FC531	0.02811	FC633	0.02329
FC219	0.02050	FC121	0.02098	FC219	0.02952	FC229	0.02064	FC219	0.02014	FC228	0.02188	FC6319	0.02329
FC6327	0.01987	FC219	0.01961	FC213	0.02787	FC219	0.01865	FC224	0.01988	FC229	0.02188	FC6318	0.02125
FC213	0.01936	FC224	0.01936	FC223	0.02642	FC224	0.01841	FC6327	0.01952	FC219	0.01976	FC6320	0.02125
FC521	0.01881	FC6327	0.01901	FC2111	0.02374	FC6327	0.01807	FC213	0.01901	FC224	0.01951	FC6325	0.02125
FC223	0.01835	FC213	0.01851	FC211	0.02127	FC344	0.01799	FC521	0.01847	FC6327	0.01915	FC6412	0.01927
FC633	0.01827	FC122	0.01850	FC212	0.02127	FC347	0.01799	FC223	0.01803	FC213	0.01866	FC6324	0.01922
FC6319	0.01827	FC521	0.01798	FC2110	0.02127	FC213	0.01760	FC633	0.01795	FC223	0.01769	FC6415	0.01793
FC224	0.01822	FC223	0.01755	FC2112	0.02044	FC521	0.01710	FC6319	0.01795	FC511	0.01764	FC228	0.01736

The sensitivity analysis of the results obtained for the use case 2, present scenario, shows that an increase of 50% in the weight of each main cluster or level I FC produced some slight changes in the top10 FCs. When the weight of level I FC safety and security is increased by 50%, 80% of the top 10 FCs remain the same. 50% increase in level I FC comfort, 70% of the top 10 FCs remain the same. For mobility, 100% for economy, 80% for the environment, and a 40% for deign option were observed. On average a 70% of the TOPI0 FCs remain the same and the results obtained are robust in the mid-term.

Table 24 shows the top10 FCs obtained for UCII in the FUTURE scenario (fully autonomous vehicles, automation level L4+) for women.

Table 24: Initial Hierarchized list of UCII FCs (Vertex 5)

FC Code	Level I FC	Level 2 FC	Level 3 FC	Norm. Weight	Rank
FC521	Environment	Emissions	Perception of reduction of ecological impact	0.03512	1
FC121	Safety and security	Human error	Perception of increased safety of AVs	0.03413	2
FC531	Environment	Public health	Perception of driving without steering wheel	0.03268	3
FC122	Safety and security	Human error	Perception of reduced safety of AVs	0.03009	4
FC224	Comfort	Simultaneity	Driving when performing simultaneous tasks in comfortable external environment	0.02500	5
FC131	Safety and security	Training	Perception of easier training needs	0.02493	6
FC511	Environment	Noise	Perception of reduction of noise	0.02051	7
FC225	Comfort	Simultaneity	Driving when performing simultaneous tasks in enriched external environment	0.01996	8
FC228	Comfort	Simultaneity	Perception of boredom	0.01934	9
FC229	Comfort	Simultaneity	Perception of joy	0.01934	9

Table 25 shows the sensitivity analysis for the vertex of the future (V5). The results in the table show the initial hierarchized list of the top 10 FCs for women as well as the top 10 FC when the weights of the level I FCs are increased by 50%. Please note that FCs in bold are those maintained from the initial hierarchy. This shows for the UC II how robust are the results presented for FUTURE scenarios (and for the profile WOMEN as a homogeneous group) in the mid and long term.

Table 25: Sensitivity analysis over time for use case II vertex 5 (Tomorrow). Note: FCs in bold are those maintained from the initial hierarchy.

Top10 for women		+50% Level I FC: Safety and security		+50% Level I FC: Comfort		+50% Level I FC: Mobility		+50% Level I FC: Economy		+50% Level I FC: Environment		+50% Level I FC: Design option	
<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>
FC521	0.03512	FC121	0.06042	FC521	0.03236	FC521	0.03356	FC521	0.03651	FC521	0.06012	FC521	0.02997
FC121	0.03413	FC122	0.05327	FC121	0.03186	FC121	0.03313	FC121	0.03615	FC531	0.05594	FC121	0.02944
FC531	0.03268	FC131	0.04414	FC531	0.03011	FC531	0.03122	FC531	0.03397	FC121	0.03614	FC531	0.02788
FC122	0.03008	FC521	0.03570	FC122	0.02809	FC122	0.02921	FC122	0.03187	FC511	0.03512	FC122	0.02595
FC224	0.02500	FC111	0.03418	FC228	0.02800	FC224	0.02526	FC224	0.02775	FC122	0.03186	FC224	0.02218
FC131	0.02493	FC112	0.03418	FC229	0.02800	FC131	0.02420	FC131	0.02641	FC224	0.02853	FC131	0.02151
FC511	0.02051	FC531	0.03322	FC219	0.02529	FC343	0.02185	FC225	0.02216	FC131	0.02640	FC6327	0.01898
FC225	0.01996	FC224	0.02951	FC224	0.02413	FC225	0.02017	FC511	0.02132	FC225	0.02278	FC225	0.01771
FC228	0.01933	FC141	0.02505	FC213	0.02387	FC511	0.01960	FC111	0.02045	FC111	0.02044	FC511	0.01750
FC229	0.01933	FC225	0.02356	FC131	0.02328	FC111	0.01874	FC112	0.02045	FC112	0.02044	FC633	0.01745

The sensitivity analysis shows that the results obtained for the autonomous vehicles of the future are robust in the mid-term since after increasing the weight of each cluster by a 50%. On average, 78% of the top 10FCs remain the same.

Use Case IV

Table 26 shows the top10 FCs obtained for UCIV in the present scenario (employment in the transport sector today) for women.

Table 26: Initial Hierarchized list of UCIV FCs (Vertex 3)

FC Code	Level 1 FC	Level 2 FC	Level 3 FC	Norm. Weight	Rank
FC313	Personal circumstances	Caring and parenting responsibilities	Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time;	0.08213	1
FC123	Socio-economic conditions	Demand factors (job recruitment)	Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed;	0.08079	2
FC255	Job characteristics	Safety and security	Security staff available to intervene in case of need.	0.04719	3
FC451	Individual characteristics	Demographic	Diversity training (re ethnicity);	0.0463	4
FC252	Job characteristics	Safety and security	Applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment;	0.04624	5
FC214	Job characteristics	HR policies	Integrate the company's commitment to gender equality into all of its communication activities and HR policies;	0.04602	6
FC115	Socio-economic conditions	Job segregation	Ensuring gender pay equality for equivalent positions;	0.04231	7
FC215	Job characteristics	HR policies	Ensure that the male–female ratio of internal promotions in different job categories is in line with the average male–female ratio of the company staff;	0.04108	8
FC133	Socio-economic conditions	Policy/legal	Family friendly policies – maternity and paternity leave;	0.04068	9
FC132	Socio-economic conditions	Policy/legal	Equal employment policies: Policies are used within the organisation to support fair recruitment and promotion processes for women, and meet national legal requirements (including Equal Employment policies);	0.03839	10

Table 27 shows the sensitivity analysis for the vertex of the present (V3). The results in the table show the initial hierarchized list of the top 10 FCs for women as well as the top 10 FC when the weights of the level I FCs are increased by 50%. Please note that FCs in bold are those maintained from the initial hierarchy.

Table 27: Sensitivity analysis over time for use case IV vertex 3 (Today). Note: FCs in bold are those maintained from the initial hierarchy.

Top10 for women		+50% Level I FC: socio-economic conditions		+50% Level I FC: job characteristics		+50% Level I FC: personal circumstances		+50% Level I FC: individual characteristics	
<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>
FC313	0.08213	FC123	0.11518	FC255	0.06598	FC313	0.12601	FC451	0.07739
FC123	0.08079	FC313	0.06505	FC252	0.06464	FC123	0.06887	FC313	0.07627
FC255	0.04719	FC115	0.06032	FC214	0.06434	FC311	0.04070	FC123	0.07503
FC451	0.04630	FC133	0.05799	FC313	0.06379	FC255	0.04023	FC255	0.04383
FC252	0.04623	FC132	0.05474	FC123	0.06275	FC451	0.03947	FC252	0.04294
FC214	0.04602	FC114	0.04919	FC215	0.05743	FC252	0.03941	FC214	0.04273
FC115	0.04231	FC131	0.04497	FC212	0.04419	FC214	0.03922	FC115	0.03929
FC215	0.04108	FC255	0.03738	FC216	0.04109	FC316	0.03819	FC215	0.03815
FC133	0.04068	FC451	0.03667	FC451	0.03596	FC115	0.03606	FC133	0.03777
FC132	0.03839	FC252	0.03662	FC242	0.03414	FC215	0.03501	FC132	0.03565

Results of the analysis show that 82% of the FCs remain in the top10 after analysing how an increase of the level 1 weight of a 50% affects the ranking; proving that the results are robust in the long term. This shows for the UC VI how robust are the results presented for PRESENT scenarios (and for the profile WOMEN as a homogeneous group) in the mid and long term.

Table 28 shows the hierarchized list of the top10 FCs obtained for UCIV in the future scenario (transport employment in the future, drone logistics) for women.

Table 28: Initial Hierarchized list of UCIV FCs (Vertex 6)

FC Code	Level 1 FC	Level 2 FC	Level 3 FC	Norm. Weight	Rank
FC123	Socio-economic conditions	Demand factors (Job recruitment)	Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed;	0.08245	1
FC313	Personal circumstances	Caring and Parenting responsibilities	Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time;	0.07124	2
FC255	Job characteristics	Safety and Security	Security staff available to intervene in case of need.	0.05037	3
FC252	Job characteristics	Safety and Security	Applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment;	0.04934	4
FC214	Job characteristics	HR policies	Integrate the company's commitment to gender equality into all of its communication activities and HR policies;	0.04911	5
FC451	Individual characteristics	Demographic	Diversity training (re ethnicity);	0.04526	6
FC215	Job characteristics	HR policies	Ensure that the male–female ratio of internal promotions in different job categories is in line with the average male–female ratio of the company staff;	0.04384	7
FC115	Socio-economic conditions	Job segregation	Ensuring gender pay equality for equivalent positions;	0.04317	8
FC133	Socio-economic conditions	Policy/Legal	Family friendly policies – maternity and paternity leave;	0.04151	9
FC132	Socio-economic conditions	Policy/Legal	Equal employment policies: Policies are used within the organisation to support fair recruitment and promotion processes for women, and meet national legal requirements (including Equal Employment policies);	0.03918	10

Table 29 shows the sensitivity analysis for the vertex of the future (V6). The results in the table show the initial hierarchized list of the top 10 FCs for women as well as the top 10 FC when the weights of the level 1 FCs are increased by 50%. Please note that FCs in bold are those maintained from the initial hierarchy.

Table 29. Sensitivity analysis over time for use case IV vertex 6 (Tomorrow). Note: FCs in bold are those maintained from the initial hierarchy.

Top10 for women		+50% Level I FC: socio-economic conditions		+50% Level I FC: job characteristics		+50% Level I FC: personal circumstances		+50% Level I FC: individual characteristics	
<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>	<i>FC</i>	<i>weight</i>
FC123	0.08244	FC123	0.11742	FC255	0.07009	FC313	0.10897	FC123	0.07701
FC313	0.07124	FC115	0.06149	FC252	0.06867	FC123	0.07217	FC451	0.07546
FC255	0.05036	FC133	0.05912	FC214	0.06835	FC255	0.04440	FC313	0.06431
FC252	0.04934	FC132	0.05580	FC123	0.06316	FC252	0.04350	FC255	0.04744
FC214	0.04911	FC313	0.05437	FC215	0.06101	FC214	0.04330	FC252	0.04647
FC451	0.04526	FC114	0.05014	FC313	0.05254	FC451	0.03933	FC214	0.04625
FC215	0.04384	FC131	0.04584	FC212	0.04695	FC215	0.03865	FC215	0.04129
FC115	0.04317	FC255	0.04020	FC216	0.04365	FC115	0.03779	FC115	0.04033
FC133	0.04151	FC252	0.03938	FC242	0.03627	FC133	0.03633	FC133	0.03877
FC132	0.03918	FC214	0.03920	FC451	0.03435	FC311	0.03520	FC132	0.03660

Results of the analysis show that overall 85% of the FCs remain in the top10 after analysing how 50% increase of the weights of level 1 FCs will affects the ranking of the hierarchized list of FCs; proving the robustness of the results in the long term. This shows for the UC VI how robust are the results presented for FUTURE scenarios (and for the profile WOMEN as a homogeneous group) in the mid and long term.

5.4 Sustainability of results over space for the profile “Women as a homogeneous group”

The aim of the analysis of the results over SPACE is to assess the validity of the DIAMOND’s results in different cultures by analysing differences in results between POLAND (East of Europe) and SPAIN (West of Europe), and compare this difference in the results with the difference in the level standard of each country. For example, by analysing how different is the Top10 FCs list between POLAND and SPAIN regarding the use of Railways public transport, and by analysing if there are significant differences between the Railways public transport of POLAND and SPAIN.

Sensitivity analysis over space for Fairness Characteristics (FC) level 1 and 2 was introduced in DIAMOND deliverable D7.2 for all the Use Cases and all the member states (DIAMOND Project, 2020b). This was addressed by DIAMOND by applying the AHP with screened data per countries (intersectional analysis per Member States or cultures, i.e. Spain, Poland, UK, France, Italy and Serbia).

In this document, we assessed the sustainability of the results over SPACE for level 3 fairness characteristics. This analysis has been performed for use case 1 and 4 in the PRESENT scenario, since these are the only two use-cases for which we have data coming from two different countries: Poland and Spain.

Use Case 1

By applying Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Bayesian Network (BN) analysis as detailed in DIAMOND deliverable D4.3, the TOP10 FCs for POLISH Women and the corresponding fairness measures can be seen in the following table:

Table 30: UCI Top 10 FCs for POLISH Women

FC Level 3	FC Code	Norm. Weight	Fairness measures
Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating)	FC323	0.03461	1. Improved seating layout that accommodates emergency exits for all users and with less dealings with other public transport users if needed. 2. Improve seating design that fulfils the need and/or with appropriation given to pregnant women, persons/carers with toddlers, disabled persons, elderly etc.
Offering adequate personal space	FC321	0.02491	1. Redesigned space within the trains that allows adequate personal space, conducive travel experience and the regulation of crowds for users of public transport whom are mothers with children, elderly, careers, disabled etc. 2. System for real-time train crowding information provision - Apps and websites highlighting less crowded carriages; Advanced solutions for platform

FC Level 3	FC Code	Norm. Weight	Fairness measures
			<p>overcrowding (wide and long platform area, improved design of tunnels, enough number of stairs, enough check-in and check-out posts), crowd controller system.</p> <p>3. Emergency call points established and for passengers available (on a number of points) emergency procedures in trains and at stations with detailed evacuation plans; enough number of emergency exits for evacuation.</p> <p>4. Staff present to provide real-time assistance to people who need assistance when they feel others are intruding on their reasonable personal space or harassing them</p>
Integration with alternative shared mobility service for last mile connections, including bike, scooter and car sharing	FC117	0.02404	Introduce special points/docks of shared mobility in each station
Availability of on-demand transport services including taxi and paratransit	FC118	0.02388	Introduce on demand transport services in each station
Availability of hospitality rooms where to ask for help in case of aggression or need;	FC317	0.02131	<p>1. The station has a hospitality room where to ask for help in case of aggression or need.</p> <p>2. There is also a phone number to call.</p>
Display advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicizing helpline numbers.	FC318	0.0210	<p>1. Advertising campaigns to avoid harassment and pickpocketing.</p> <p>2. Advertising campaigns with helpline numbers.</p> <p>3. People attending the help line should be trained on equality and gender.</p>
Appropriate height steps or step-free access to trains;	FC2110	0.02088	Station design that allows for appropriate heights or step-free access to trains for people with caring responsibilities and (dis)abilities
Safe and easily accessible drop-off and pick-up points;	FC216	0.02079	Accessible and safe drop-off and pick-up points at stations
Signposting with bright colour contrasting and large font to help people with visual impairment;	FC215	0.02076	Availability of clear and visible signposting with large font and bright colours to assist people with visual impairment
Safe and step free pedestrian crossings and sidewalks surrounding the stations;	FC217	0.02073	Presence of step free and safe pedestrian crossing and sidewalks surrounding the station suitable for parents with young children, elderly and people with (dis)abilities

In the same way, the TOPI0 FCs for SPANISH Women and their corresponding fairness measures are the next:

Table 31: UCI Top 10 FCs for SPANISH Women

FC Level 3	FC Code	Norm. Weight	Fairness measures
Availability of on-demand transport services including taxi and paratransit	FC118	0.02971	Introduce on demand transport services in each station
Integration with alternative shared mobility service for last mile connections, including bike, scooter and car sharing	FC117	0.02843	Introduce special points/docks of shared mobility in each station
Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating).	FC323	0.02764	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improved seating layout that accommodates emergency exits for all users and with less dealings with other public transport users if needed. 2. Improve seating design that fulfils the need and/or with appropriation given to pregnant women, persons/carers with toddlers, disabled persons, elderly etc.
Display advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicizing helpline numbers.	FC318	0.02674	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Advertising campaigns to avoid harassment and pickpocketing. 2. Advertising campaigns with helpline numbers. 3. People attending the help line should be trained on equality and gender.
Number of service available within the transport infrastructure	FC115	0.02593	<p>The next services are displayed in the station</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. There is an APP or similar, with updated information about when the next train is reaching a station 2. Increase the connection services with the metropolitan area (more frequency, wider timetable,...) 3. Enhance multimodality with other complementary shifts of transport: Bus, bike-sharing, ... (agreements about timetables, fees, common electronic tools, etc...) 4. Agreements with car-sharing companies for door-to-door services in the case of disabilities or reduced mobility. 5. Systematically introduce accessibility planning system for disadvantaged groups, those with special requirements (e.g. those with prams) and disadvantaged locations (e.g. rural, poor areas) to identify services (times, costs, connecting services etc.) and gaps in the services at times they are required 6. Provide smaller buses and improve the frequency of the services
Availability of hospitality rooms where to ask for help in case of aggression or need;	FC317	0.02583	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The station has a hospitality room where to ask for help in case of aggression or need. 2. There is also a phone number to call.

FC Level 3	FC Code	Norm. Weight	Fairness measures
Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc.	FC116	0.02427	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adapted connection paths and access points to all users (including people with reduced mobility, women with children...). 2. Facilitate to travel with bikes and scooters. Put safety docks for bike and scooters parking. 3. More engagement with local transport partners. 4. Regular travel surveys with travellers focusing on intermodality issues or concerns, frequency of service etc.
Visibility of the surrounding area of the station;	FC315	0.02333	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Remove visual obstacles. 2. Increase lightning in the stations and their surroundings. 3. Improve the signalling for easy wayfinding. 4. Include video and audible information.
Safe and step free pedestrian crossings and sidewalks surrounding the stations;	FC217	0.02205	Presence of step free and safe pedestrian crossing and sidewalks surrounding the station suitable for parents with young children, elderly and people with (dis)abilities
Ramps and escalator with enough room to carry shopping bags, baby strollers, luggage and wheelchair to access the station and transfer within the stations;	FC212	0.02193	Ensure equal access to all in the stations and facilities for disabled people and people travelling with children in pushchairs as per the EU Code of Practice. Design Standards for Accessible Railway Stations

In general, 60% of the top 10 FCs are found to be the same for users of Spanish and Polish railway service. The FCs common to both countries are:

- ◆ FC323 Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating).
- ◆ FC117 Integration with alternative shared mobility service for last mile connections, including bike, scooter and car sharing
- ◆ FC118 Availability of on-demand transport services including taxi and paratransit
- ◆ FC317 Availability of hospitality rooms where to ask for help in case of aggression or need;
- ◆ FC318 Display advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicizing helpline numbers.
- ◆ FC217 Safe and step free pedestrian crossings and sidewalks surrounding the stations;

On the other hand, the main differences between these TOP10FCs for each country are:

- ◆ Poland (ZTM users):
 - FC321 Offering adequate personal space
 - FC2110 Appropriate height steps or step-free access to trains
 - FC216 Safe and easily accessible drop-off and pick-up points
 - FC215 Availability of clear and visible signposting with large font and bright colours to assist people with visual impairment

- ◆ SPAIN (FGC users):
 - FC115 Number of service available within the transport infrastructure
 - FC116 Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc
 - FC315 Visibility of the surrounding area of the station
 - FC212 Ramps and escalator with enough room to carry shopping bags, baby strollers, luggage and wheelchair to access the station and transfer within the stations

An ANOVA test on the Observations checklist data for POLAND and SPAIN has been performed in order to analyse the differences between the stations of the two companies. After the analysis we conclude that there are significant differences, from a statistical point of view, between both infrastructures' levels. Results of the analysis can be seen in Annex I

Under the hypothesis that the SPANISH railways infrastructure has approximately the level of FGC railways stations and the POLISH railways infrastructure has approximately the level of ZTM railways infrastructures, we can conclude that the POLISH and the SPANISH railways infrastructures are significantly different.

The 40% difference in TOP10 FCs observed for the POLISH and SPANISH women could be due to the significant differences between the POLISH and the SPANISH railways infrastructures.

Use Case IV

Similar to use-case I, after applying AHP and the BN analysis (refer to DIAMOND deliverable D4.3 for details), the TOP10 FCs for POLISH Women and the corresponding fairness measures regarding a fair transport can be seen in the following table:

Table 32: UCIV Top 10 FCs for POLISH Women

FC Level 3	FC Code	Norm. Weight	Fairness measures
Employees with small children to choose whether or not to continue working overtime;	FC314	0.05879	1. Opportunity for remote/home and flexible working to suit caring responsibilities when the job position permits it.
Diversity training (re ethnicity)	FC451	0.05557	1. Company internal and external communication and marketing should show the diversity 2. To have ready a written CSR protocol / policy 3. Include in the annual training plans training on CSR aspects on annual basis (harassment policy, whistle blowing procedure, disciplinary actions, etc...) 4. Regular and updated training available. Evaluations of training conducted regularly 5. Employers and HR personnel should be trained to effectively handle diversity issues in recruitment and at the work place
Ensure employment decisions are based on objective issues related to the job	FC125	0.05069	Establish blind CVs and evaluation procedures for recruitment, promotion and definition of training needs for each employee, including e.g. templates with objectives issues to evaluate for each position.

FC Level 3	FC Code	Norm. Weight	Fairness measures
Strategic skills development framework	FC411	0.04412	Develop a formal policy focused on promoting women skills development
Supported career/carer breaks	FC311	0.04204	Special provisions can also be allowed to facilitate parents in taking care of sick kids, or to the care of other dependents such as elderly.
Improved maternity provisions and re-entry policy	FC216	0.04010	Monitor and increase support for those returning to work and ensure that they fully re-engage with training and promotion programme and systems. Ensure Employees have access to fair and quality maternity provision and return to work processes.
Regulations and education regarding sexual harassment between colleagues	FC251	0.03746	Applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment
Continuous workplace training and lifelong learning	FC414	0.03536	Policy on equal access to training, and development opportunities for employees returning from leave of absence
Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed;	FC123	0.03512	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Blind selection process of CV, to avoid stereotypes predetermined for selection of new applicants. In the first steps of the recruitment process, avoid name and gender. 2. Avoid genderize the employment advertisements. Language and images gender neutral 3. Infrastructures and organization policies are ready for all genders (change rooms, toilets, dresses,...) 4. Choice of publication for advertisement 5. Base levels made for each role i.e. 5 men and 5 women. 6. Use wide range of media for adverts and stress women working in stereotypically male jobs. 7. Ensure adverts in social media are not allocated by algorithms that reinforce stereotypes (e.g. advertising mechanics in female orientated sites rather than just male orientated sites).
Public transport and flexible and adaptable jobs;	FC323	0.03512	Alleviate the heavy workload for physical jobs and making the working conditions more attractive.

In the same way, the TOPI0 FCs for SPANISH Women and their corresponding fairness measures are shown below:

Table 33: UCIV Top 10 FCs for SPANISH Women

FC Level 3	FC Code	Norm. Weight	Fairness measures
Supported career/carer breaks	FC311	0.05110	Special provisions can also be allowed to facilitate parents in taking care of sick kids, or to the care of other dependents such as elderly.
Have access to funds to travel to work	FC321	0.04714	Give funds to employees to travel to work
Part-time work, flexible working hours, and work from home options	FC316	0.04660	When possible and needed give the opportunity/facilitate to employees part-time working options, flexible working hours and work from home options
Employees with small children to choose whether or not to continue working overtime	FC314	0.04455	1. Opportunity for remote/home and flexible working to suit caring responsibilities when the job position permits it.
Affordable child/social care	FC322	0.04307	Affordable child/social care provided and/or childcare or kindergartens facilities within or near the company premises.
Public transport and flexible and adaptable jobs	FC323	0.04301	Alleviate the heavy workload for physical jobs and making the working conditions more attractive.
Ensure employment decisions are based on objective issues related to the job	FC125	0.03842	Establish blind CVs and evaluation procedures for recruitment, promotion and definition of training needs for each employee, including e.g. templates with objective issues to evaluate for each position.
Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time	FC313	0.03171	1. When possible, approve telematic work if required by the employee. 2. When this is not possible (site operators), outline contingency plans per each shift to cover punctual absences by an employee. 3. Staff to get notice of shifts well in advance, so they can change them. Ability of staff to change shift patterns at short notice to reflect caring needs.
Regulations and education regarding sexual harassment between colleagues	FC251	0.03051	Applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment

FC Level 3	FC Code	Norm. Weight	Fairness measures
Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed	FC123	0.03027	1. Blind selection process of CV, to avoid stereotypes predetermined for selection of new applicants. In the first steps of the recruitment process, avoid name and gender. 2. Avoid genderize the employment advertisements. Language and images gender neutral 3. Infrastructures and organization policies are ready for all genders (change rooms, toilets, dresses,...) 4. Choice of publication for advertisement 5. Base levels made for each role i.e. 5 men and 5 women. 6. Use wide range of media for adverts and stress women working in stereotypically male jobs. 7. Ensure adverts in social media are not allocated by algorithms that reinforce stereotypes (e.g. advertising mechanics in female orientated sites rather than just male orientated sites).

60% of the top 10 FCs were found to be the same for employees of Spain and Poland railway service. These common FCs to develop a fair transport working environment and more inclusive for women are:

- ◆ FC314 Employees with small children to choose whether or not to continue working overtime
- ◆ FC125 Ensure employment decisions are based on objective issues related to the job.
- ◆ FC311 Supported career/carer breaks
- ◆ FC251 Regulations and education regarding sexual harassment between colleagues
- ◆ FC323 Public transport and flexible and adaptable jobs
- ◆ FC123 Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed

On the other hand, the main differences between these TOP10FCs for each country are:

- ◆ Poland:
 - FC451 Diversity training (re ethnicity)
 - FC411 Strategic skills development framework
 - FC216 Improved maternity provisions and re-entry policy
 - FC414 Continuous workplace training and lifelong learning
- ◆ Spain:
 - FC321 Have access to funds to travel to work
 - FC316 Part-time work, flexible working hours, and work from home options
 - FC322 Affordable child/social care
 - FC313 Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time

Results show that Polish employees give higher importance to diversity training, the development of skills and continuous training as well as an improvement of maternity provisions and policies. In the case of Spanish employees in addition to the common priorities, they also define as priorities to attract more women to the transport sector facilitating the travelling to work, facilitate more

flexible working conditions, give the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce the working time and make child/social care options affordable to transport employees.

In this case, we cannot raise the hypothesis that labour conditions of FGC and ZTM cannot be extrapolated respectively to Spanish and Polish labour conditions, and consequently differences between both companies cannot be used to explain or justify these differences of at least half of relevant factors for women regarding the employment as has been shown after the AHP and BN analysis. No other technical resource has been found to provide an explanation or justification to these differences in the TOP10 factors for the Use-case 4 between POLISH and SPANISH women.

6. Replicability of Results to Other Transport Context

The Diamond Toolbox was designed to be used by transportation companies, governments and other interested parties to fill gaps in women's equity data in the transportation world.

The toolbox is based on 4 use cases, and the main themes are: 1. Capacity to meet required needs; 2. Accessibility; 3. Safety and security.

Use case I: Public transport infrastructures. Railways.

The objective of the Use-Case I is to improve the quality of the railway infrastructure, in particular of the railway stations, from a gender perspective, understanding the needs of women in terms of accessibility, comfort and safety within the stations but also in the entrances to the station. In particular, the main critical issues addressed for the three sections are:

- a. CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users):
 - ◆ Reliability and efficiency;
 - ◆ Service and efficiency for commuting;
 - ◆ Service and efficiency access to point of interest for all users;
 - ◆ Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc;
 - ◆ Wayfinding information;
 - ◆ Service and efficiency;
 - ◆ Service reliability;
 - ◆ Wayfinding information and integration with other modes of public transport;
 - ◆ Stations integration with other modes of public transport;
 - ◆ Integration with other modes of public transport;
 - ◆ Design;
 - ◆ Directions in stations;
 - ◆ Improved ventilation and air-conditioning;
- b. ACCESSIBILITY (for all users):
 - ◆ Location of station;
 - ◆ Reliability and efficiency;
- c. SAFETY AND SECURITY (for all users):
 - ◆ Harassment and pickpocketing;
 - ◆ Design;
 - ◆ Display advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicizing helpline numbers;
 - ◆ Overcrowding and emergency management.

The issues addressed in this relative use case are critical aspects of all transport systems (Cascetta, 2001; Meyer, 2016) They are more strongly focused on serving the needs of all users, the role of safety in the planning process, and transportation planning in the context of societal concerns, including the development of more sustainable transportation solutions.

The content structure has been redesigned with a new format that promotes a more functionally driven multimodal approach to planning, design, and implementation, including guidance toward the latest tools and technology. In particular, the toolbox related to this USE CASE I could be used in its entirety for the road transport system such as buses, and for the local maritime

transport system such as ferries. By excluding the item relating to "Service and efficiency for commuting", this USE CASE I can be extended to the air and maritime transport system in general.

Use case II: Autonomous Vehicles

The goal of Use-Case II is to increase the level of acceptance of women towards autonomous driving technology. In particular, the main critical issues addressed for the three sections are:

- a. CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (of drivers):
 - ◆ Multi-tasking;
 - ◆ Travel time;
 - ◆ Vehicle behaviour;
- b. ACCESSIBLE (for all drivers):
 - ◆ Vehicle shape (getting in and out of the car);
 - ◆ Vehicle shape (seating);
 - ◆ Vehicle shape (shopping/suitcases);
 - ◆ Human Machine Interface (ergonomics);
 - ◆ Human Machine Interface (warning and communication system);
- c. SAFETY AND SECURITY (for all users):
 - ◆ Trust in technology;
 - ◆ Human Errors - Specific training for AV drivers;
 - ◆ Safe ergonomics.

In this Use Case, very generic aspects have been evaluated leaving out some more pertinent points of automated vehicle HMIs.

The in-vehicle human-machine interface (HMI) serves as a communication bridge between the vehicle and the driver and its careful design plays a decisive role to ensure the effectiveness and the safety of such systems.

The way information is presented, as well as the correct timing of alerts are two crucial factors for the design of warning systems (Cao et al., 2009). A promising way to reduce transmission errors and to enhance system effectiveness is to present information using multiple modalities, e.g. visual, acoustic, or haptic driver feedback (Schwarz and Fastenmeier, 2017; Naujoks et al., 2019).

Use case III: Bike-sharing services

The goal of Use-Case III is to increase the use of bicycle sharing by women. In particular, the main critical issues addressed for the three sections are:

- a. CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users):
 - ◆ Suitable bikes for those traveling with children, carrying packages and shopping;
 - ◆ Promote cycling as a legitimate form of transportation in BAME communities;
 - ◆ Bikes suited to local topography and weather conditions;
 - ◆ Available to those in low-income neighbourhoods;
- b. ACCESSIBILITY (for all users):
 - ◆ Location of docking stations, proximity and convenience;

- ◆ Costs including membership fees;
 - ◆ Service reliability;
 - ◆ Public awareness of scheme;
 - ◆ Simple and flexible signing-up process;
 - ◆ Payment option;
 - ◆ Sheltered docking stations;
- c. SAFETY AND SECURITY (for all users):
- ◆ Presence of CCTV systems to improve user perception of security;
 - ◆ Separate biking infrastructure;
 - ◆ Personal safety – maintenance of bikes;
 - ◆ Safety equipment provided including helmets, hi-vis vest, ponchos;
 - ◆ Ease of reporting problems/complaints about bike-sharing facilities.

The issues addressed summarize the main issues relating to sharing mobility. In concrete terms, sharing mobility translates into car sharing, bike sharing, scooter sharing, and similar methods of sharing (Roukouni et al., 2021). The Use-Case III can be easily be used in field like car-sharing, scooter sharing, and similar services of sharing.

The issues addressed summarize the main issues relating to bike-sharing (Antoniades and Chrysanthou, 2009). However, an important aspect is not addressed: bike-sharing system integrated into public transport. This aspect would especially help women with children, who if there were problems such as fatigue, would have the opportunity to use the public transport system, such as bus or metro.

Use case IV: Employment

The goal of Use-Case IV is to increase the participation of women as employees in the transport sector, including off-site professional positions - vehicle drivers, maintenance technicians and other currently less attractive positions for women. In particular, the main critical issues addressed for the three sections are:

- a. CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all employees):
- ◆ Promotion and development opportunities;
 - ◆ Family friendly working conditions;
 - ◆ Training, work environment & culture;
 - ◆ Salary and conditions;
- b. ACCESSIBILITY (for all potential employees) :
- ◆ Recruitment of women;
 - ◆ Specific training and career development for women;
 - ◆ Design;
- c. SAFETY AND SECURITY (for all frontline employees):
- ◆ HR Policies gender awareness and anti-bullying;
 - ◆ Personal Protection Equipment suitable for women.

In this use case, the main problems related to gender equality were addressed as reported by the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE, 2016). The proposed solutions are inherent to good practices in the European Commission's final report (2019). Given the general character and inherence to a broader form of Gender Equality, this USE CASE IV can also be extended to other forms jobs like motor vehicle drivers, building frame and related trade workers, managers of small enterprises, construction, physical and engineering science technicians and machinery mechanics.

Results

The structure of the toolbox is very flexible and well organized, systematically addressing the various problems and organizing them in three parts: Capacity to meet required needs; Accessibility; Safety and security. Through this flexibility and organization, the toolbox can be extended to some domains, for example:

- ◆ The Use-Case I (Public transport infrastructures. Railways) can be easily used in fields like aviation, logistic or maritime transport;
- ◆ The Use-Case III (Bike-sharing services) can be easily used in fields like scooter sharing and similar services of sharing.
- ◆ The Use-Case IV (employment of women in jobs related with the transport system) can be easily used in fields like motor vehicle drivers, building frame and related trade workers, managers of small enterprises, construction, physical and engineering science technicians and machinery mechanics.

From the analysis of the toolbox and the different USE-Cases, direct impacts with other domains emerged.

In Use Case I, the issues relating to the capacity to meet required needs are closely related to other transport systems like aviation, logistic or maritime transport. Improving these aspects for the railway system has benefits for the other connected transport systems. Furthermore, the aspects relating to accessibility are closely related to urban design, considering the Location of station, in terms of “the level of comfort and security of the transport infrastructures by walking” and “the public transport services nearby the transport infrastructures accessible with comfortable walking distance”. The improvement of these aspects implies a change from the point of view of urban architecture. Where new urban rail systems are built, there are expectations from them, such as an increase in public transport usage, a reduction in car traffic, and betterment of air quality. In addition, urban rail investment is often expected to have some impacts on land-use and urban development, such as new development in the city centre and in economically depressed areas, and a pattern of urban growth which is public-transport oriented (Babalik, 2000; Babalik, 2002). Other studies have also shown that an enhanced transport system has a positive impact on local tourism (Pagliara et al., 2015; Pagliara et al., 2017; Della Corte and Aria, 2014; Coronado et al., 2013; Mimeur et al., 2013; Delaplace et al., 2013)

The USE Case III tackles the problem of bike-sharing. Promote or enhance the bike sharing system can be defined in terms of reducing carbon-dioxide emissions, smoothing traffic flows and encouraging a healthier commute to and from work for human beings (Zhang et al., 2015). Though to make bike-sharing systems sustainable, it has been highlighted those three fundamental interrelated factors: the exogenous factors such as bike-ability and safety; the institutional ownership types; and the physical design factors (OBIS, 2011). Recent studies showed that bike-sharing is highly attractive for potential tourists as part of a short urban holiday, as a frequent activity for multiple purpose (Kaplan et al., 2015; Caulfield et al., 2017). Therefore, cities that consider expanding their attraction as tourist destinations could benefit from bike-sharing schemes and bicycle infrastructure as an integral part of the touristic experience and could use the cycling experience as part as their branding strategy (Kaplan et al., 2015).

7. Legislation and Standards' opportunities for the sustainability of Diamond outputs

The transport sector is traditionally a male chauvinist both in terms of employment and the values it embodies. Women are the largest public transport users worldwide, but the presence of many barriers limit their mobility. The number of women employed in the transport sector both as operators as well as that engineers or managers remains very low. The integration of the gender perspective in transport is a critical aspect and has become the nucleus of public debate in many industrialized countries.

Worldwide, gender has begun to feature as a recognized issue in transport policy and planning while transport has begun to feature on the agenda of gender policy. "Gender and transport" is therefore a somewhat new professional field. At present, it is fair to argue that there are no systematic gender inclusion procedures for transport, neither in terms of training of professionals, participation of users nor the design and planning of systems, services and equipment (UNECE, 2021). Although there is no mandatory legislation, the DIAMOND project encompasses these critical issues by proposing solutions.

7.1 Opportunities related with standards

Even though there are not standards strictly related to the DIAMOND toolbox, the broader context of the project complies with several international standards such as:

- ◆ NEXT GENERATION EU 24/07/2020: "PROMOTING GENDER EQUALITY AND WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT". This Gender Equality Strategy frames the European Commission's work on gender equality and sets out the policy objectives and key actions for the 2020-2025 period. It aims at achieving a gender equal Europe where gender-based violence, sex discrimination and structural inequality between women and men are a thing of the past. A Europe where women and men, girls and boys, in all their diversity, are equal. Where they are free to pursue their chosen path in life, where they have equal opportunities to thrive, and where they can equally participate in and lead our European society. In the next EU budget (2021-2027), gender equality-related projects will be supported and funded through a range of EU programs: from specific grants under the Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values program to the major Funds structural, social and cohesion of the EU.
- ◆ EN ISO 26000:2020. This standard aims to eliminate bias and promote parity through recommending that organizations have a balanced mix of men and women in governing structures and management, ensure both sexes are treated equally when it comes to recruitment, career opportunities and pay, and make sure the needs of men and women are given equal consideration in company decisions and activities. This International Standard provides guidance on the underlying principles of social responsibility, recognizing social responsibility and engaging stakeholders, the core subjects and issues pertaining to social responsibility and on ways to integrate socially responsible behaviour into the organization. It is not a management system standard and is not intended for certification purposes, nor for regulatory or contractual purposes.

- ◆ GRI 405: DIVERSITY AND EQUAL OPPORTUNITY 2016. This Standard is part of the series of GRI Sustainability Reporting Standards (GRI Standards). These Standards are intended to be used by organizations to report on their impacts on the economy, the environment and society. When an organization actively promotes diversity and equal opportunities at work, it can produce significant benefits both for the organization itself and for the workers. For example, the organization can access a larger and more heterogeneous set of potential workers. These benefits also flow to society at large, as greater equality promotes social stability and supports further economic development.
- ◆ ISO 30415:2021 Human Resources Management – Diversity and Inclusion. ISO 30415 aims to represent a guide on Diversity and Inclusion for organizations, Governance, the Board, collaborators and stakeholders. It is aimed at all types of organizations: public, private, non-profit, regardless of the size or type of activity. This international standard identifies a series of principles, roles and responsibilities, actions, policies, processes, practices and measures to enable and support effective diversity and inclusion in the workplace. In this sense, ISO 30415 represents a model that allows organizations to start a process of continuous improvement of inclusive capacities and enhancement of diversity. An organization that decides to conform its Diversity Management business process to the requirements of ISO 30415 acquires an important competitive advantage on the market. In fact, in recent years a lot of attention has been paid to the inclusive capacity of companies as this involves an increase in cultural stimuli and business culture in general, developing greater economic value and greater attractiveness for investors.
- ◆ UN Agenda 2030, Goal 5: Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls. Goal 5 aims to achieve equal opportunities between women and men in economic development, the elimination of all forms of violence against women and girls (including the abolition of forced and early marriages) and equality of rights at all levels of participation:
 - End all forms of discrimination against women and girls everywhere.
 - Eliminate all forms of violence against women and girls, both in the private and public spheres, including trafficking in women and sexual and any other kind of exploitation.
 - Eliminate all abusive practices such as arranged marriage, the phenomenon of child brides and female genital mutilation.
 - Recognize and enhance unpaid care and domestic work, providing a public service, infrastructure and social protection policies and the promotion of shared responsibilities within families, in accordance with national standards.
 - Guarantee full and effective female participation and equal leadership opportunities at all decision-making levels in the political, economic and public life spheres.
 - Ensure universal access to sexual and reproductive health and reproductive rights, as agreed in the Program of Action of the International Conference on Population and Development and the Beijing Platform for Action and the documents produced in subsequent conferences.
 - Initiate reforms to give women equal rights of access to economic resources as well as ownership and control of land and other forms of ownership, financial services, inheritance and natural resources, in accordance with national laws.
 - Strengthen the use of enabling technologies, in particular information and communication technologies, to promote women's empowerment.

- Adopt and intensify a sound policy and applicable legislation for the promotion of gender equality and the empowerment of all women and girls, at all levels.
- SQAS (Safety and Quality assessment system) (www.sqas.org): This is an assessment scheme in an European level addressed to the logistic service providers of the chemical industry based on modular questionnaires according to the activity (transport service, warehouse, tank cleaning operations and chemical distribution). There are some sections addressing Corporate Social Responsibility issues where gender equity related to human resources policies such as training, promotion and recruitment is assessed. Companies offering services to the chemical industry are being assessed on this scheme every 3 years and for sure the implementation of the recommendations provided by the Diamond toolbox will help them to improve the score of these assessments.

The use of the DIAMOND toolbox by organizations and companies produces an important competitive advantage on the market. In recent years, attention has been given to the inclusive capacity of companies as this involves an increase cultural and business culture in general, developing greater economic value and greater attractiveness for investors.

In a summary, the next table shows the opportunities that current certifications and standards are offering to the exploitation of the Diamond Toolbox:

Table 34: Certification Standards Opportunities

Standard	Territorial scope	Certifiable/assessed by an external body?	Certification details	Affected subsector
NEXT GENERATION EU 24/07/2020	European	No	n.a	all
EN ISO 26000:2020	European	Yes	Accredited Bodies	all
GRI 405: DIVERSITY AND EQUAL OPPORTUNITY 2016	European	NO	n.a	all
ISO 30415:2021	European	YES	Accredited Bodies	all
UN Agenda 2030, Goal 5	European	No	n.a	all
SQAS	European	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • www.sqas.org • There is a list of accredited assessors in www.sqas.org 	Logistic service providers related to the chemicals logistics

7.2 Opportunities related with legislation

At European and national level there are various directives or laws that they promote equal opportunities and equal treatment of women and men in employment and occupation. Below are some of the main European and national standards:

- ◆ **Directive 2002/73/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 September 2002 amending Council Directive 76/207/EEC on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and promotion, and working conditions.** This European Directive obliges Member States, in accordance with national traditions and practices, to take appropriate measures to encourage dialogue between the social partners in order to promote the principle of equal treatment, inter alia through monitoring of practices in the workplace, collective agreements, codes of conduct, research or exchanges of experiences and good practices.
- ◆ **Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006 on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation (recast).** This European Directive consolidates and modernizes the previous directives provides a specific legal basis for the adoption of measures Community aimed at ensuring the application of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment in matters of employment and occupation, including the principle of equal pay for the same work or work of equal value.
- ◆ **Council Directive 79/7/EEC of 19 December 1978 on the progressive implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women in matters of social security.** This European Directive obliges Member States to take the necessary measures to remove laws, regulations and administrative provisions which are contrary to the principle of equal treatment.
- ◆ **Directive 2010/41/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 7 July 2010 on the application of the principle of equal treatment between men and women engaged in an activity in a self-employed capacity and repealing Council Directive 86/613/EEC.** This European Directive guarantees the application in the Member States of the principle of equal treatment between men and women who are self-employed or who contribute to the exercise of self-employment.
- ◆ **Council Directive 2004/113/EC of 13 December 2004 implementing the principle of equal treatment between men and women in the access to and supply of goods and services.** The purpose of this European Directive is to establish a framework for combating discrimination based on sex with regard to access to and supply of goods and services, in order to make the principle of equal treatment for men effective in the Member States and women.
- ◆ **Council Directive 92/85/EEC of 19 October 1992 on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health at work of pregnant workers and workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding.** This European Directive has as its object the implementation of measures to promote the improvement of the safety and health at work of pregnant workers, workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding.
- ◆ **Real Decreto 901/2020, de 14 de octubre, por el que se regulan los planes de igualdad y su registro y se modifica el Real Decreto 710/2010, de 28 de mayo, sobre registro y depósito de convenios y acuerdos colectivos de trabajo.**

This Spanish National regulation obligates to all companies with more than 50 employees in Spain to develop and officially register an equity plan addressing gender aspects. The minimum technical requirements of this equity plan are defined in this regulation. The Diamond Toolbox is a good tool to develop fairness measures adapted to specific profiles in this mandatory equity plan.

- ◆ **Decreto Legislativo 30 maggio 2005, n. 145 - Attuazione della direttiva 2002/73/CE in materia di parità di trattamento tra gli uomini e le donne, per quanto riguarda l'accesso al lavoro, alla formazione e alla promozione professionale e le condizioni di lavoro (G.U. n. 173 del 27.07.2005).** This Italian decree supplements the provisions already in force concerning the implementation of the principle of equal treatment between men and women and the promotion of equality through positive actions, as regards access to employment, professional training and promotion and working conditions.
- ◆ **LEGGE 12 luglio 2011, n. 120 - Modifiche al testo unico delle disposizioni in materia di intermediazione finanziaria, di cui al decreto legislativo 24 febbraio 1998, n. 58, concernenti la parità di accesso agli organi di amministrazione e di controllo delle società quotate in mercati regolamentati. (11G0161) (G.U. Serie Generale n.174 del 28.07.2011).** The Italian law, having acknowledged the situation of chronic imbalance in the representation of genders in the top positions of the aforementioned companies, intends to rebalance access to top management in favor of women.
- ◆ **LEGGE 23 novembre 2012, n. 215- Disposizioni per promuovere il riequilibrio delle rappresentanze di genere nei consigli e nelle giunte degli enti locali e nei consigli regionali. Disposizioni in materia di pari opportunità nella composizione delle commissioni di concorso nelle pubbliche amministrazioni. (12G0237) (G.U. Serie Generale n.288 del 11.12.2012).** The Italian provision aims at the rebalancing of gender representations in the councils and councils of local authorities and in regional councils and introduces provisions on equal opportunities in the composition of competition commissions in public administrations.
- ◆ **Loi n° 2006-340 du 23 mars 2006 relative à l'égalité salariale entre les femmes et les hommes (I).** The French law on equal pay introduces the obligation to negotiate measures to eliminate the differences in remuneration.
- ◆ **Loi n° 2011-103 du 27 janvier 2011 relative à la représentation équilibrée des femmes et des hommes au sein des conseils d'administration et de surveillance et à l'égalité professionnelle (I).** The French law requires the share of directors or members of the supervisory board of each sex cannot be less than 20%.
- ◆ **Lov 9. juni 1978 nr. 45 om likestilling mellom kjønnene (likestillingsloven).** Article 21 provides for the mandatory representation of women in the commissions of public bodies, company committees, company boards of directors, etc.
- ◆ **Lov om samvirkeforetak - Act (No. 81 of 2007) relating to cooperative societies.** In Norway, the art. 69 of this law provides for the mandatory representation of women in the commissions of public bodies, company committees, company boards of directors, etc.

In other European countries, such as Germany, the United Kingdom and Sweden, there are no rules on the representation of women in listed companies, only "recommendations" in their respective corporate governance codes.

In a summary, the next table shows the opportunities that current certifications and standards are offering to the exploitation of the Diamond Toolbox:

Table 35: Legislation Opportunities

Regulation	Link to access the regulation	Territorial scope	Bullet points facilitating the exploitation of Diamond outputs	Affected businesses
Directive 2002/73/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 September 2002	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32002L0073&from=IT	All Europe	Implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and promotion, and working conditions	All member states of EU
Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32006L0054	All Europe	The implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation (recast)	All member states of EU
Directive 79/7/EEC	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A31979L0007	All Europe	The progressive implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women in matters of social security.	All member states of EU
Directive 2010/41/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32010L0041	All Europe	Application of the principle of equal treatment between men and women engaged in an activity in a self-employed capacity	All member states of EU
COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2004/113/EC OF THE EUROPEAN UNION	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32004L0113	All Europe	the principle of equal treatment between men and women in the access to and supply of goods and services	All member states of EU
Council Directive 92/85/EEC	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A31992L0085	All Europe	Measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health at work of pregnant workers and workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding	All member states of EU

Table 35: Legislation Opportunities-Continuation

Regulation	Link to access the regulation	Territorial scope	Bullet points facilitating the exploitation of Diamond outputs	Affected businesses
Real Decreto 901/2020, de 14 de octubre	Link	Spain	Obligation to develop and implement an equity plan addressing gender aspects	All companies with more than 50 employees
Legislative Decree 145 of May 30, 2005	https://www.camera.it/parlam/leggi/deleghe/05145dl.htm	Italy	Equal treatment for men and women with regard to access to employment, training and career advancement and working conditions	All companies or public administration
Lex 120 of July 12, 2011	https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2011/07/28/011G0161/sg	Italy	The pink quotas imposed on the Boards of Directors	Companies listed on financial markets
Lex 215 of November 23, 2012	https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2012/12/11/012G0237/sg	Italy	Rebalancing of gender representations in councils and councils of local authorities and regional councils	Public administration
La legge n°83-635 del 13/7 1983	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loida/id/JORFTEXT00000504474/	France	Principle of equality for hiring, remuneration, promotion, training.	All companies
Lex 340 of March 23, 2006	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loida/id/JORFTEXT000000816849/	France	Wage parity introduces the obligation to renegotiate measures to eliminate the differences in remuneration	All companies
Lex 103 of January 27, 2011	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loida/id/JORFTEXT000023487662/	France	It promotes professional equality between men and women within the company and requires the search for a "balanced representation between men and women"	Companies listed on the stock exchange, public sector companies and public entities of an industrial and commercial nature subject to private law
Lex 45 of June 9, 1978	https://www.regjeringen.no/no/dokumenter/likes_tillingsloven/id454568/	Norway	Gender equality in public bodies commissions, works councils, company boards of directors, etc.	Companies and public administration
Lex 81 of June 29, 2007	http://www.ilo.org/dyn/natlex/natlex4.detail?p_lang=en&p_isn=88380	Norway	Gender equality on boards of directors.	Companies and public administration

8. Conclusion

From the equity analysis of the FCs for each use-case, it is found that for UCI, the ranking of FMs significantly differs from that of effectiveness and efficiency the most important FCs relates to accessibility of the stations (such as ramps, escalators and lifts for persons with disabilities) which corresponds to “FC114: Adapt the station access with ramps, escalators and lifts for users with special needs.”, “FC112: Coordinated timetables between the different transport modes in the stations.” and “FC111: Availability of information that indicate and allows access to key destination”. The most important fairness measures in use-case II, education about sportive driving mode “FC637: Education about sportive driving mode when it is activated: Benefits and disadvantages”, “FC6327: Automated system for speed controlling” and “FC219: Dissemination and promotional campaigns about safety mechanisms in the case of bad weather.” have a higher equity score. Similarly, use-case III, FCs “FC237: Provide recommendations to customers with alternative routes avoiding high-speed roads from point A to B, “FC312: Separate cycle lanes free from vehicular traffic” and “FC332: Safe cycle routes for cycling with children” are the highest rank FCs in the achieving equity in the se of bike-sharing. Regarding UCIV, two of the most important FMs from the aspect of equity are the measure that relates to CSR protocol readiness “FC451: To have ready a written CSR protocol / policy” and FC313: Ability of staff to change shift patterns at short notice to reflect caring needs”

The results show that 43% of FCs remained the in the top 10 FCs from the analysis of Vertex 1 of the Inclusion Diamond (Public transport Today) and 67% for Vertex 3 (Public transport tomorrow, under the futuristic scenario of Hyperloop). The results indicate 20-80% of the top 10 FCs changed in the hierarchized list in both vertexes, therefore the TOP10 FCs in the **USE CASE I** are sustainable in the **mid-term**.

The results show that 70% of FCs remained the in the top 10 FCs of Vertex 2 of the Inclusion Diamond (autonomous driving under L4+) and 78% for Vertex 4 (autonomous driving over L4+). The results indicate that less than 20% of the top 10 FCs changed from the analysis in both vertexes. Therefore, the TOP10 FCs of **USE CASE II** are sustainable in the **mid-term**.

Similarly, the results show that 82% of FCs remained the in the top 10 FCs of Vertex 3 of the Inclusion Diamond (employment Today) and 85% for Vertex 6 (employment tomorrow, under the futuristic scenario of employment based on logistics of drones). These indicate that less than 20% of the TOP 10 FCs changed from the analysis in both vertexes. Hence, the TOP10 FCs in the **USE CASE IV** are shown to be sustainable in the **long-term**.

The finding of the **sustainability** analysis indicates that the TOP10 FCs are robust over CULTURES or SPACE and over TIME:

40% of TOP10 FCs for POLISH and SPANISH women are **different** in the **USE CASE I**, perhaps due to the significant difference between the POLISH and the SPANISH railways infrastructures, as has been shown after the ANOVA analysis.

In the same way, **40%** of TOP10 FCs for POLISH and SPANISH women are **different** in the **USE CASE IV**, but in this case we do not have the technical resource to explain or justify this observed difference.

The findings of the use-cases were found to be applicable in other transport context; Use-Case I (Public transport infrastructures. Railways) can be easily extended and used in fields like aviation, logistic or maritime transport. Use-Case III (Bike-sharing services) can be easily used in fields like scooter sharing and similar services of sharing. Use-Case IV (employment of women in jobs related

with the transport system) can be easily used in fields like motor vehicle drivers, building frame and related trade workers, managers of small enterprises, construction, physical and engineering science technicians and machinery mechanics.

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Annex I: Results ANOVA. Use case I. Polish (ZTM) and Spanish (FGC) stations

Table 36: UCI ANOVA Analysis

		FC Code	F	P-value	F critical	Remarks
Are there alternative shared mobility services for last mile connections (e.g. bike, scooter and car sharing)?	OSA1. Alternative mobility services	FC117	176.495	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there on-demand transport services including taxi and paratransit?	OSA2. On demand transport	FC118	159.691	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are the drop-off and pick-up points safe and easily accessible?	OSA3. Safety & Accessibility drop-off pick up	FC216	565.642	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are the pedestrian crossings and sidewalks surrounding the stations safe and step free?	OSA4. Safe-step free pedestrian crossings	FC217	2.535	0.112	3.852	Not Significant
How adequate is the lighting in the surrounding area of stations? (AM, natural lighting)	OSA5. Lightning surroundings-natural	FC2112	47.216	0.000	3.852	Significant
How adequate is the lighting in the surrounding area of stations? (PM, artificial lighting)	OSA6. Lightning surroundings-Artificial	FC2112	2.317	0.128	3.852	Not Significant
Are there car and moto public parking places?	OSA7. Parking availability	FC239	50.965	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there bicycles storage facilities and bicycles racks?	OSA8. Bike racks/storage	FC2310	69.863	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are the pedestrian routes between transit modes weather protected? (where applicable)	OSA9. Weather protected routes mode change	FC2311	443.872	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are the waiting areas for buses, taxis, etc sheltered?	OSA10. Sheltered waiting areas other modes	FC2312	25.499	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there police and security personnel including women police? (to be a deterrent for perpetrators)	OSA11. Security personnel	FC314	26.076	0.000	3.852	Significant
How is the level of visibility of the surrounding area of the station? (AM, natural lighting)	OSA12. Visibility surroundings-Natural light	FC315	16.458	0.000	3.852	Significant
How is the level of visibility of the surrounding area of the station? (PM, artificial lighting)	OSA13. Visibility surroundings-Artificial light	FC315	1.776	0.183	3.852	Not Significant
Are there services available within the transport infrastructure (e.g. shop, pharmacy, newsstand)?	OCL14. Services availability	FC115	15.144	0.000	3.852	Significant

		FC Code	F	P-value	F critical	Remarks
Are the travel updates through video announcements clear and timely?	OCL15. Travel info-clear	FC121	234.412	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are the travel updates through video announcements provided in multiple languages?	OCL16. Travel info-Multilanguage	FC121	14.271	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are the travel updates through audible announcements clear and timely?	OCL17. Travel info-Audible-clear	FC121	57.096	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are the travel updates through audible announcements provided in multiple languages?	OCL18. Travel info-Audible-Multilanguage	FC121	19.669	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are the timetable and network map user-friendly, intuitive and easily understandable?	OCL19. Easy timetable-map	FC122	53.167	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there information points, enquiry desks, help desks, security desks?	OCL20. Info desk	FC123	0.001	0.978	3.852	Not Significant
Are there vertical and horizontal signposting for easy wayfinding?	OCL21. Signalling	FC124	153.184	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there information regarding positive environmental contribution?	OCL22. Environmental info	FC126	61.153	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there electronic ticket and flexible payment methods using cash, card, smartphones and mobile apps?	OCL23. Flexible payment	FC136	788.815	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there ATMs, ticket machines, ticket office and alternative sale points?	OCL24. Alternative sale points	FC137	111.515	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there lift with enough room to carry shopping bags, baby strollers, luggage and wheelchair?	OCL25. Space needs	FC211	0.005	0.946	3.852	Not Significant
Are there ramps and escalator with enough room to carry shopping bags, strollers, luggage and wheelchair?	OCL26. Ramps-escalator space	FC212	1.788	0.182	3.852	Not Significant
Are there tactile surfaces to provide wayfinding information to people with reduced visual capabilities?	OCL27. Tactile surfaces-wayfinding	FC214	129.231	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there signposting with bright colour contrasting and	OCL28. Signalling-Adequate visual impaired	FC215	499.221	0.000	3.852	Significant

		FC Code	F	P-value	F critical	Remarks
large font to help people with visual impairment?						
Are the ticket machines positioned at convenient height for a wide variety of users?	OCL29. Ticket machine-convenient height	FC218	24.790	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are the wayfinding info positioned at convenient height for a wide variety of users?	OCL30.Height wayfinding info	FC218	24.790	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there fare gates to accommodate a wide variety of users?	OCL31. Fare gates	FC219	120.880	0.000	3.852	Significant
How adequate is the lighting in the stations? (AM, natural lighting)	OCL32. Lightning station-natural	FC2112	406.793	0.000	3.852	Significant
How adequate is the lighting in the stations? (PM, artificial lighting)	OCL33. Lightning station-artificial	FC2112	18.175	0.000	3.852	Significant
Is the environment clean and hygienic?	OCL34. Clean environment	FC221	0.233	0.629	3.852	Not Significant
Are there waste baskets?	OCL35. Waste basket	FC222	144.920	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there waste recycling baskets?	OCL36. Recycling basket	FC222	61.153	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there deterioration, graffiti and vandalism?	OCL37. Deterioration Graffiti	FC223	13.707	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there separated toilets for women?	OCL38. Women toilets	FC231	202.673	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there waiting areas with seating arrangements?	OCL39. Waiting areas	FC233	21.008	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there baby changing facilities in both men and women toilets?	OCL40. Baby changing facilities	FC234	104.448	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there breastfeeding facilities?	OCL41. Breast feeding facilities	FC235	9.764	0.002	3.852	Significant
Are there vending machines?	OCL42. Vending machines	FC236	139.635	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there left luggage and lost property offices?	OCL43. Lost object office	FC237	9.597	0.002	3.852	Significant
Is there Wi-Fi or 3G/4G connection?	OCL44. Wi-Fi	FC238	1245.811	0.000	3.852	Significant
Is the CCTV system available and visible?	OCL45. CCTV	FC312	336.641	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there SOS emergency phones?	OCL46. SOS phones	FC313	90.685	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there police and security personnel including women	OCL47. Security personnel	FC314	394.247	0.000	3.852	Significant

		FC Code	F	P-value	F critical	Remarks
police? (to be a deterrent for perpetrators)						
Are there complaint Information in case of violations to personal safety?	OCL48. Complaint info personal safety	FC316	55.835	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there hospitality rooms where to ask for help in case of aggression or need?	OCL49. Hospitality rooms-aggressions	FC317	234.412	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicising helpline numbers?	OCL50. Advertisements public awareness helpline number	FC318	84.942	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are the travel updates through video announcements clear and timely?	OPL51. Travel info-clear - Platform	FC121	88.095	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are the travel updates through video announcements provided in multiple languages?	OPL52. Travel info-Multilanguage-Platform	FC121	54.556	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are the travel updates through audible announcements clear and timely?	OPL53. Travel info-Audible-clear-Platform	FC121	65535.000	#DIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Are the travel updates through audible announcements provided in multiple languages?	OPL54. Travel info-Audible-Multilanguage-Platform	FC121	65535.000	#DIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Are the timetable and network map user-friendly, intuitive and easily understandable?	OPL55. Easy timetable-map-Platform	FC122	9.764	0.002	3.852	Significant
Are there vertical and horizontal signposting for easy wayfinding?	OPL56. Signalling-Platform	FC124	114.594	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there lift with enough room to carry shopping bags, baby strollers, luggage and wheelchair?	OPL57. Space needs-Platform	FC211	3.836	0.050	3.852	Not Significant
Are there ramps and escalator with enough room to carry shopping bags, strollers, luggage and wheelchair?	OPL58. Ramps, escalator space-Platform	FC212	2.232	0.136	3.852	Not Significant
Are there tactile surfaces to provide wayfinding information to people with reduced visual capabilities?	OPL59. Tactile surfaces, wayfinding Platform	FC214	508.843	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there signposting with bright colour contrasting and large font to help people with visual impairment?	OPL60. Signalling-Adequate visual impaired Platform	FC215	647.663	0.000	3.852	Significant

		FC Code	F	P-value	F critical	Remarks
Are the wayfinding info positioned at convenient height for a wide variety of users?	OPL61.Height wayfinding info-Platform	FC218	188.926	0.000	3.852	Significant
How adequate is the lighting in the stations? (AM, natural lighting)	OPL62. Lightning station-natural Platform	FC2112	584.435	0.000	3.852	Significant
How adequate is the lighting in the stations? (PM, artificial lighting)	OPL63. Lightning station-artificial-Platform	FC2112	185.743	0.000	3.852	Significant
Is the environment clean and hygienic?	OPL64. Clean environment-Platform	FC221	9.764	0.002	3.852	Significant
Are there waste baskets?	OPL65. Waste basket-Platform	FC222	185.112	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there waste recycling baskets?	OPL66. Recycling basket-Platform	FC222	65535.000	#iDIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Are there deterioration, graffiti and vandalism?	OPL67. Deterioration Graffiti-Platform	FC223	212.401	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there waiting areas with seating arrangements?	OPL68. Waiting areas-Platform	FC233	47.216	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there vending machines?	OPL69. Vending machines-Platform	FC236	685.459	0.000	3.852	Significant
Is there Wi-Fi or 3G/4G connection?	OPL70. Wi-Fi-Platform	FC238	1084.350	0.000	3.852	Significant
Is the CCTV system available and visible?	OPL71. CCTV-Platform	FC312	247.593	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there SOS emergency phones?	OPL72. SOS phones	FC313	545.251	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are there police and security personnel including women police? (to be a deterrent for perpetrators)	OPL73. Security personnel-Platform	FC314	720.305	0.000	3.852	Significant
Are the travel updates through video announcements clear and timely?	OC74. Clear video info	FC121	65535.000	#iDIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Are the travel updates through video announcements provided in multiple languages?	OC75. Video-Multilanguage	FC121	65535.000	#iDIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Are the travel updates through audible announcements clear and timely?	OC76. Travel info-Audible-clear-Carriage	FC121	65535.000	#iDIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Are the travel updates through audible announcements provided in multiple languages?	OC77. Travel info-Audible-Multilanguage-Carriage	FC121	65535.000	#iDIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant

		FC Code	F	P-value	F critical	Remarks
Are the timetable and network map user friendly, intuitive and easily understandable?	OC78. Easy timetable-map-Carriage	FC122	65535.000	#iDIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Are there bright colour handrail to help people with visual impairment to identify support quickly?	OC79. Bright handrail -visual impaired	FC213	65535.000	#iDIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Is access to trains with appropriate height steps or step-free?	OC80. Height steps train access	FC2110	65535.000	#iDIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Are handles suited at convenient height for all users or vertical grab bars?	OC81. Handles/Bars	FC2111	65535.000	#iDIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Is the environment clean and hygienic?	OC82. Clean environment-Carriage	FC221	65535.000	#iDIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Are there deterioration, graffiti and vandalism?	OC83. Deterioration-Graffiti-Carriage	FC223	65535.000	#iDIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Are there allocated seats to pregnant women, parents with young children and elderly?	OC84. Pregnant-elderly seats	FC232	185.112	0.000	3.852	Significant
Is there Wi-Fi or 3G/4G connection?	OC85. Wi-Fi-carriage	FC238	65535.000	#iDIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Is the CCTV system available and visible?	OC86. CCTV-Carriage	FC312	65535.000	#iDIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Are there SOS emergency phones?	OC87. SOS phones-Carriage	FC313	65535.000	#iDIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Are there police and security personnel including women police? (to be a deterrent for perpetrators)	OC88. Security personnel-Carriage	FC314	1084.350	0.000	3.852	Significant
Is there improved ventilation and air-conditioning?	OC89. Air conditioning-Carriage	FC322	65535.000	#iDIV/0!	3.852	Not Significant
Is there improved layout of seating? (longitudinal seating allows more privacy)	OC90. Seating layout	FC323	15.205	0.000	3.852	Significant